

POSTER ABSTRACTS

WORLD INVENTIA PUBLISHERS

An International Publishing House

<http://www.worldinventiapublishers.com>

Abstracts are Publishing in

**JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC
RESEARCH IN PHARMACY**

ISSN: 2277-9469

<http://www.jsrponline.com>

**Vol - 8 Supplement - 1
September - 2019**

www.worldinventiapublishers.com

1st International Conference on
**Current Research & Innovations
in Healthcare Systems**

(CRIHS-2K19)

In Association with

Indian Pharmaceutical Association (IPA-GSB)
Goa State Branch, Goa

CRIHS-2K19

September 27-28, 2019
Goa, India

Sponsored by

KP Labs, Hyderabad

Venue: Conference Hall, 1st Floor, Ravindra Bhavan Margao,
Opposite SH 5, Fatorda, Margao, Goa - 403602.

www.wipintercons.com

1st INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON

“Current Research & Innovations in Healthcare Systems, GOA”

(CRIHS – 2K19)

ABSTRACT PROCEEDINGS

Organised by

WIP INTER CONS

Hyderabad – 500035, Telangana, INDIA.

In Association with

**Indian Pharmaceutical Association – Goa State Branch
(IPA-GSB)**

TABLE OF CONTENT FOR SELECTED ABSTRACTS

ABSTRACT CODE	CORRESPONDING AUTHER	TITLE OF ABSTRACT	PAGE NO.
PHARMACEUTICS – (CRIHS – CEU)			
CRIHS-CEU-001	N. Shiva Krishna	PREPARATION AND EVALUATION OF PRESS COATED TABLETS BY PULSATILE DELIVERY SYSTEM OF DEXLANSOPRAZOLE	S-1
CRIHS-CEU-002	Murali R	FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF IMMEDIATE RELEASE TABLET OF TERBINAFINE HYDROCHLORIDE	S-2
CRIHS-CEU-003	Irfan Ansari	DEVELOPMENT OF DARUNAVIR PRO-LIPOSOME POWDER FOR ORAL DELIVERY BY USING BOX-BHENKEN DESIGN: A POTENTIAL APPROACH FOR DELIVERY OF DRUGS HAVING HIGH FIRST-PASS METABOLISM	S-3
CRIHS-CEU-004	Mahesh Rindhe	DEVELOPMENT & EVALUATION OF MATRIX TYPE SUSTAINED RELEASE TABLET OF LAMIVUDINE BY USING NATURAL POLYMERS	S-4
CRIHS-CEU-005	Madasu Susmitha	PHARMACEUTICAL MANAGEMENT - 3D PRINTING OF TABLET MANUFACTURING	S-5
CRIHS-CEU-006	Swezel Pereira	DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF IN-SITU GEL FOR NASAL DELIVERY OF ANTI-MIGRAINE DRUG IN COMBINATION WITH ANTI-EMETIC DRUG	S-6
CRIHS-CEU-007	Shreya Naik	DESIGN, DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTERIZATION OF DRUG LOADED PULSINCAP DEVICE FOR THE TREATMENT OF AMOEBIASIS	S-7
CRIHS-CEU-008	Ankita A. Poy Raiturcar	DESIGN, DEVELOPMENT AND OPTIMIZATION OF LIPOSOMES FOR PULMONARY DRUG DELIVERY OF ISONIAZID	S-8
CRIHS-CEU-009	Anisha R. Naik	DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF GASTRORETENTIVE FLOATING DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM OF HAEMATINIC AGENT	S-9
CRIHS-CEU-010	Dr. S. Naazneen	CERAMOSIDES AS ORAL MOISTURIZERS	S-10
CRIHS-CEU-011	Riya A. Hegde	MODIFIED CO-POLYMER WITH DUAL RESPONSIVE ACTIVITY FOR ANTI-CANCER DRUG DELIVERY	S-11
CRIHS-CEU-012	B. Nagarani	DEVELOPMENT AND <i>IN VITRO</i> EVALUATION OF SITAGLIPTIN MUCOADHESIVE TABLETS FOR NIDDM	S-12
CRIHS-CEU-013	Aishwarya Parvatkar	DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF ORAL DOSAGE FORMULATIONS OF AN ANTIEMETIC DRUG USING NATURAL CARRIERS	S-13
CRIHS-CEU-014	Punita Naik	FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF ELEUSINE CORACANA EDIBLE MEDICATED JELLIES FOR THE DELIVERY OF PARACETAMOL	S-14
CRIHS-CEU-015	Ankita Bhangui	DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF NOVEL TRANSUNGUAL PATCH FOR THE TREATMENT OF ONYCHOMICOSIS	S-15
CRIHS-CEU-016	Swana Dias	LEPIDIUM SATIVUM AS A NOVEL POLYMER FOR SUSTAINED RELEASE SYSTEMS	S-16
CRIHS-CEU-017	Gunda Mahesh	FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF A DENTAL GEL CONTAINING THE ACTIVE PRINCIPLE'S OF <i>MIMUSOPS ELENGI</i> AGAINST ORAL PATHOGENS	S-17
CRIHS-CEU-018	Tejal Chaudhari	DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF MULTIFUNCTIONAL NATURAL POLYMER FROM SEEDS OF <i>DELONIX REGIA</i>	S-18
CRIHS-CEU-019	Bharti Gotmare	FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF MICROSPONGE BASED ORNIDAZOLE SUSTAINED RELEASE TABLET	S-19
CRIHS-CEU-020	Hashweta Gawde	PILL CAMERA: NEW EMERGING TREND IN DIAGNOSIS	S-20
CRIHS-CEU-021	Marfa Sheikh	RECENT ADVANCES IN COATING TECHNOLOGY	S-21
CRIHS-CEU-022	Swati Yearimani	A REVIEW ON ROBOTS IN PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRY; A	S-22

		TOOL TO INCREASE PRODUCTIVITY	
CRIHS-CEU-023	Yashodita Desai	AUTOMATION AND DIGITALIZATION IN PHARMACEUTICALS	S-23
CRIHS-CEU-024	B. Manjula	DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF MODIFIED RELEASE SOLID ORAL DOSAGE FORM (TOLCAPONE)	S-24
CRIHS-CEU-025	B. Anvesh	DESIGN AND CHARACTERISATION OF ACECLOFENAC MULTIPARTICULATE COLON TARGETED DRUG DELIVERY	S-25
CRIHS-CEU-026	Ch. Prasanna	PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF EXTENDED RELEASE MATRIX TABLETS OF BISOPROLOL FUMERATE USING NATURAL AND SYNTHETIC POLYMERS	S-26
CRIHS-CEU-027	Ch. Sai Priya	EVALUATION OF ANALGESIC AND ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY OF <i>CITRUS LIMON</i> PEEL IN ALBINO WISTAR RATS	S-27
CRIHS-CEU-028	Y. Sravanthi	POLYSACCHARIDE INDUCED PRODUCTION OF SILVER NANOPARTICLES (AG-NPS) AND THEIR ANTIBACTERIAL EFFICACY AGAINST SELECTED BACTERIAL PATHOGENS	S-28
CRIHS-CEU-029	N. Sreeja	FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF INJECTION OF POORLY SOLUBLE DRUG USING MIXED SOLVENCY CONCEPT	S-29
CRIHS-CEU-030	Puja Rathod	ROLE OF POLYMERIC INTERACTIONS IN SOLUBILITY ENHANCEMENT OF ETODOLAC BY USING MILLING AND HOT MELT EXTRUSION TECHNIQUE	S-30
CRIHS-CEU-031	Rajendra Prasad R	PROLIPOSOME BASED TRANSDERMAL DELIVERY OF KETOCONAZOLE	S-31

PHARMACEUTICAL CHEMISTRY – (CRIHS - CHEM)

CRIHS-CHEM-001	Lakshminarayanan	SYNTHESIS AND IN VIVO BIOLOGICAL EVALUATION OF NOVEL CHALCONES WITH METHYL SULPHONYL END AS POTENT ANTI-INFLAMMATORY AGENTS	S-32
CRIHS-CHEM-002	Arifa Begum SK	ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF THE NOVEL FATTY ACYL CONJUGATES OF ROSUVASTATIN	S-33
CRIHS-CHEM-003	S. Jayaseelan	A CHEMOMETRIC ASSISTED RP-HPLC METHOD FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF CHLORDIAZEPOXIDE AND AMITRYPTYLINE HYDROCHLORIDE IN BULK AND PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM	S-34
CRIHS-CHEM-004	Devi Thamizhanban	DISSOLUTION METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF NAPROXEN FROM FIXED DOSE COMBINATION OF NAPROXEN AND ESOMEPRAZOLE MAGNESIUM IN DELAYED RELEASE TABLETS	S-35
CRIHS-CHEM-005	Sanelly Pereira	METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR THE BIOANALYSIS OF AN ANTIHYPERTENSIVE DRUG USING LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY COUPLED WITH TANDEM MASS SPECTROMETRY	S-36
CRIHS-CHEM-006	Shubham Joshi	BIOANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR A DIURETIC DRUG BY LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY TANDEM MASS SPECTROMETRY	S-37
CRIHS-CHEM-007	Mithun Rudrapal	DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF ANALYTICAL METHODS FOR THE ESTIMATION OF CURCUMIN IN THE HERBAL FORMULATION OF <i>HARIDRA</i> BY UV-VIS SPECTROPHOTOMETRY AND RP-HPLC	S-38
CRIHS-CHEM-008	J. Sushmitha	REVERSE PHASE HIGH PERFORMANCE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHIC TECHNIQUE FOR THE DETERMINATION OF METFORMIN IN PURE AND ITS DOSAGE FORMS	S-39

PHARMACOGNOSY – (CRIHS - COG)

CRIHS-COG-001	Karthika. S	PHYTOCHEMISTRY AND PHYTOCONSTITUENTS OF <i>HYDROCOTYLE JAVANICA</i> AND <i>PERISTROPHE BICALYCVLATA</i>	S-40
---------------	-------------	---	------

CRIHS-COG-002	Anoopa John L	PHYTOCHEMICAL, ANTI-OXIDANT AND ANTHELMINTIC ACTIVITIES OF AERIAL PARTS OF <i>ERANTHEMUM CAPENSE LINN</i>	S-41
CRIHS-COG-003	Bodapati Laxmi Manasa	BIO QUALITY BOOSTER EXTRACTION OF BIOWAX FROM PLANTS FOR COMMERCIAL APPLICATION	S-42
CRIHS-COG-004	P. Kavitha Baburao	IN VITRO AND IN VIVO ANTIHYPERGLYCEMIC EFFECT OF ICHNOCARPUS FRUTESCENCES, COMMERCIALY IMPORTANT MEDICINAL PLANT USED IN INDIAN TRADITIONAL MEDICINE	S-43
CRIHS-COG-005	Gauri Pai Angle	PHYTOCHEMICAL INVESTIGATION THE ROOTS OF ICHNOCARPUS FRUTESCENS	S-44
CRIHS-COG-006	Tadka H	EVALUATION OF NIRGUNDI TAILA	S-45
CRIHS-COG-007	Naik A	EVALUATION OF TRIPHALA GUGGULU	S-46
CRIHS-COG-008	Desai MS	EVALUATION OF VASA GHRITA	S-47
CRIHS-COG-009	A. Rajesh	PHARMACOGNOSTICAL EVALUATION AND QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS OF <i>BOERHAAVIA DIFFUSA</i> L. ROOTS	S-48
CRIHS-COG-010	K. Madhu	PRELIMINARY PHYTOCHEMICAL AND IN VITRO ANTIOXIDANT PERSPECTIVES OF THE LEAF EXTRACTS OF AZIMA TETRACANTHA LAM (FAMILY: SALVADORACEAE)	S-49
CRIHS-COG-011	G. Sangeetha	PROTECTIVE EFFECTS OF PHYLLANTHUS FRUIT EXTRACT IN ADRIAMYCIN INDUCED GENOTOXICITY IN BONE MARROW CELLS OF MICE	S-50

PHARMACOLOGY – (CRIHS - COL)

CRIHS-COL-001	H. Seena	INVITRO AND INVIVO ANTI DIABETIC ACTIVITY OF METHANOLIC EXTRACT OF AERIAL PARTS OF ALANGIUM SALVIFOLIUM SUBSPECIE HEXAPETALUM (WANGERIN)	S-51
CRIHS-COL-002	Ch. Madhav Kalyan	ASSESSMENT OF INSULIN RESISTANCE IN DIABETIC FAMILIES	S-52
CRIHS-COL-003	Tenali Poojitha	TEAR METABOLOMICS AN NEW EMERGING TOOL TO DIAGNOSE DRY EYE DISEASE	S-53
CRIHS-COL-004	Adapa Prathyusha	A PROSPECTIVE OBSERVATIONAL STUDY ON SAFETY AND EFFECTIVENESS OF ESCITALOPRAM Vs DESVENLAFAXINE IN THE TREATMENT OF ANXIETY DISORDERS	S-54
CRIHS-COL-005	Sahitya Uppada	TOPICAL CADEXOMER IODINE VERSUS SALINE DRESSING IN THE MANAGEMENT OF ACUTE AND CHRONIC EXUDING WOUNDS	S-55
CRIHS-COL-006	Chaitanya. D	DRUG UTILISATION EVALUATION & COST ANALYSIS OF ANTI-EMETIC DRUGS PRESCRIBED IN ONCOLOGY WARD IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL	S-56
CRIHS-COL-007	Ganesh. B	THE IMPACT OF METABOLIC SYNDROME ON RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS: A COHORT STUDY	S-57
CRIHS-COL-008	Beeram Poorna Sivani	EMERGING TRANSDERMAL TREATMENT IN PSYCHIATRY	S-58
CRIHS-COL-009	B. Prashanthi	A STUDY ON INCIDENCE OF PRE-ECLAMPSIA AND ITS NEONATAL OUTCOME	S-59
CRIHS-COL-010	Ch. Shilpa	A STUDY ON MATERNAL AND FETAL OUTCOME ON OLIGOHYDRAMNIOUS PATIENTS	S-60
CRIHS-COL-011	Dr. K. Hemamalini	EVALUATION OF ANTIDEPRESSANT ACTIVITY OF <i>SPIRULINA PLATENSIS</i>	S-61
CRIHS-COL-012	A. Shwetha	EPIDERMODYSPLASIA VERRUCIFORMIS	S-62
CRIHS-COL-013	V. Shivani	A STUDY OF MEDICATION ERRORS IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL	S-63
CRIHS-COL-014	D. Gayathri	THE CONCEPT OF ALLOSTASIS	S-64
CRIHS-COL-015	B. Prashanth Naidu	EVALUATION OF RATIONAL USE OF ANTIBIOTICS FOR SURGICAL PROPHYLAXIS	S-65
CRIHS-COL-016	Soujanya Srinivas	PREVALENCE OF SUB-CLINICAL HYPOTHYROIDISM AMONG DIABETES MELLITUS PATIENTS WITH VASCULAR COMPLICATIONS	S-66
CRIHS-COL-017	KL. Keerthana	MANAGEMENT AND TREATMENT OF CEREBRAL PALSY IN	S-67

		CHILDREN	
CRIHS-COL-018	V. Manisha	EFFECTS OF BLOOD GLUCOSE LEVELS WERE STUDIED BY USING CANDESARTAN CILEXETIL AND GLIMIPIRIDE IN NORMAL AND DIABETIC ALBINO MALE RATS	S-68
CRIHS-COL-019	Aniruddha Banerjee	A STUDY OF FRESH FRUIT JUICE OF (HYBRID PERCENTAGE)- <i>MALUS DOMESTICA X M.SYLVESTRIS</i> AGAINST EXPERIMENTALLY INDUCED ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE IN MICE	S-69
CRIHS-COL-020	Grinton Veigas	EVALUATION OF ANTI-ANXIETY ACTIVITY OF AQUEOUS EXTRACT OF PUMPKIN (<i>CUCURBITA MAXIMA</i>) SEEDS IN MICE	S-70
CRIHS-COL-022	T. Somasekhar	PHARMACOLOGICAL SCREENING AND PHYTOCHEMICAL EVALUATION OF ANTI-DIABETIC ACTIVITY OF <i>ASPARAGASUS RACEMOSUS</i> LEAVES IN NORMAL AND ALLOXAN INDUCED DIABETIC RATS	S-71
CRIHS-COL-023	Rajesh Oruganti	A RETROSPECTIVE OBSERVATIONAL STUDY ON THE ASSESSMENT AND TREATMENT PATTERN OF DIFFERENT TYPES OF EPILEPTIC SEIZURES IN PEDIATRICS	S-72

GENERAL PHARMA – (CRIHS - GEN)

CRIHS-GEN-001	K. Sreevasudha	SOFT SKILLS - A MOMENTOUS FOR PHARMACY STUDENTS	S-73
CRIHS-GEN-002	G. Sravani	3D-BIOPRINTING - REVOLUTIONARY TECHNOLOGY: A BRIEF FOCUS	S-74
CRIHS-GEN-003	Sumaiyya Mehreen	WHAT DO YOU THINK WILL HAPPEN TO "CANCER" IN COMING "10 YEARS"? - THE UPCOMING INNOVATION: CANCER CELL TO FAT CELL	S-75
CRIHS-GEN-004	Dr. A. Rajani	POSTPARTUM DEPRESSION - A REVIEW	S-76
CRIHS-GEN-005	Kokonda Soundarya	AMYGDALIN (VITAMIN B ₁₇) - A REVIEW ON ANTICANCER PROPERTY	S-77
CRIHS-GEN-006	Shailaja Ande	CRISPR-THE NEW TOOL IN THE GENE EDITING TO PREVENT CANCER	S-78
CRIHS-GEN-007	Shailaja Ande	GREEN BLOOD	S-79
CRIHS-GEN-008	Shailaja Ande	INJECTABLE BONE CEMENT	S-80
CRIHS-GEN-009	Shailaja Ande	SKIN GLUE	S-81
CRIHS-GEN-010	Kavitha Baburao	METAGENESIS TO ADIPOGENESIS	S-82
CRIHS-GEN-011	G. Charitha	INNOVATION IN MOBILE HEALTH CARE TECHNOLOGY	S-83
CRIHS-GEN-012	V. Veeramanikandan	BASICS ASPECTS OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS	S-84
CRIHS-GEN-013	R. Murali Krishnan	LEADS AND DANGERS OF BIOSIMILARS	S-85
CRIHS-GEN-014	V. Mallikarjun	A STUDY ON REGISTRATION OF GENERIC DRUGS AND REGULATORY REQUIREMENTS FOR MIDDLE EAST COUNTRIES	S-86
CRIHS-GEN-015	J. Manashwini	ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE-THE BEGINNING OF A NEW ERA IN PHARMACY PROFESSION	S-87

NURSING – (CRIHS - NUR)

CRIHS-NUR-001	R. Chaudhary	EFFECT OF NESTING AND SWADDLING ON SLEEP DURATION OF PRETERM NEONATE	S-88
---------------	--------------	--	------

EDITORIAL REPORT

**Dr. Madhukar Akkala, M.Pharm., Ph.D,
(Editor-in-Chief)**

World Inventia Publishers

<http://www.worldinventiapublishers.com/>

“Modern Medical advances have helped millions of people live Longer, Healthier lives”

“We owe these improvements to decades of investment in Medical Research”

The department of Pharmaceutical, Medical, Pharmacology, Dental, Biotechnology, Microbiology, Agricultural, Ayurvedic, Chemistry, Computer and Engineering Technology and all Life Sciences takes immense delectation in organizing and releasing our Conference proceedings.

Our coalesced effort delves further into the latest and recent research and developments in Pharmaceutical, Medical, Pharmacology, Dental, Biotechnology, Microbiology, Agricultural, Ayurvedic, Chemistry, Computer and Engineering Technology and all Life Sciences fields.

Our goal is to encourage researchers, academicians and students to come up with their original work and enlighten their thoughts with other presentations. Keeping the above in mind we have put together the conference proceedings with the work of various authors in their areas of research.

CRIHS-CEU-001

PREPARATION AND EVALUATION OF PRESS COATED TABLETS BY PULSATILE DELIVERY SYSTEM OF DEXLANSOPRAZOLE

N. Shiva Krishna ^{1*}, Dr. B. Jayanthi ², Dr. A. Madhukar ³

^{1*} Department of Pharmaceutics, St Marys Pharmacy College, Deshmukhi, Hyderabad, Telangana, INDIA.

² Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacy, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar, Chidambaram, Tamilnadu, INDIA.

³ Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacy, MRM College of Pharmacy, Hyderabad, Telangana, INDIA..

Email: shivakrishna.pharmacy1969@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Pulsatile drug delivery system releases the drug during early hours when the patient takes the formulation at bed time. Thus, the patient compliance can be increased by pulsatile drug delivery. Pulsatile drug delivery was prepared by press coated method to mimic the circadian rhythm of the disease by releasing the drug with a distinct pre-determined lag time of 8 hours. The inner core tablets were prepared by using direct compression method. All the ingredients such as Dexamethasone, Sodium Starch glycolate, Lycoat, Croscollon, where dry blended for 20 minutes followed by addition of Magnesium Stearate. The mixture was blended further 10 minutes. 9 formulations (F1-F9) of the core were prepared by using Lycoat, CP, & SSG as disintegrants in different proportions (2, 4 & 6%). The drug compatible with all the excipients. All the parameters were in the optimum range. Among the 9 formulations F6 containing CP (6%) as disintegrant showed a better drug release of 99.87% over 25 minutes was selected. 200mg of resultant powder blend was manually compressed at a pressure of 100 tablets, with 8mm punch and die to obtain the core tablet. The core was coated with Karaya gum, HPMC K100 and Pectin with different polymer ratios (P1F6-P7F6). Among these P6F6 was optimized based on the lag time and percent of drug release (98.43% of drug release in 8 hours).

KEYWORDS: Press Coated Tablets, Dexamethasone, Croscollon, Lycoat, Sodium Starch Glycolate, HPMC K100, Karaya gum, Pectin.

How to cite this Abstract:

N. Shiva Krishna, Dr. B. Jayanthi, Dr. A. Madhukar. PREPARATION AND EVALUATION OF PRESS COATED TABLETS BY PULSATILE DELIVERY SYSTEM OF DEXLANSOPRAZOLE. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-1.

CRIHS-CEU-002

FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF IMMEDIATE RELEASE TABLET OF TERBINAFINE HYDROCHLORIDEMurali R^{1*}, Srinivasan N¹, Selvamuthukumar R¹, Nitin Panicker² and A. Mohankumar¹¹ Department of Pharmacy, Annamalai University, Chidambaram, Tamilnadu, INDIA.² Cipla Ltd, Mumbai, INDIA.Email: aumuralir@rediffmail.com**ABSTRACT**

The immediate release tablet of antifungal drug Terbinafine hydrochloride were prepared, developed and evaluated to increase solubility and bioavailability of low soluble drug by using wet granulation method. The tablets were prepared by varying concentrations and compositions of microcrystalline cellulose, sodium starch glycolate, hydroxyl propyl methyl cellulose, magnesium stearate, and colloidal silicon dioxide of seven trial batches. The drug excipient compatibility study was studied by photostability study. No significant changes were observed in photo stability study. The tablets were evaluated for disintegration test, content uniformity, and friability. Invitro drug release profile Terbinafine hydrochloride was examined in four different media pH 0.1N HCL, pH 4.5 acidic buffers, pH 6.8 phosphate buffer and pH 3.0 citrate buffer for 45 minutes. The drug release for trial batch no.7 shows 100.4% of drug release and innovator shows 102% of drug release. Stability study was conducted on tablets of batch 6 and 7 as per the ICH guidelines and FDA guidelines. The formulation trial no 6 and 7 showed no significant changes during the study period of accelerated stability study for 3 months. The study is concluded that result of formulation 7 showed that good developed formulation of immediate release tablet containing Terbinafine hydrochloride drug was similar to the marketed product with all respect and stable to effect of temperature and humidity.

KEYWORDS: Immediate release, Terbinafine hydrochloride, Photostabilty, In-vitro drug release.**How to cite this Abstract:**

Murali R, Srinivasan N, Selvamuthukumar R, Nitin Panicker and A. Mohankumar. FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF IMMEDIATE RELEASE TABLET OF TERBINAFINE HYDROCHLORIDE. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-2.

CRIHS-CEU-003

DEVELOPMENT OF DARUNAVIR PRO-LIPOSOME POWDER FOR ORAL DELIVERY BY USING BOX-BHENKEN DESIGN: A POTENTIAL APPROACH FOR DELIVERY OF DRUGS HAVING HIGH FIRST-PASS METABOLISM

Irfan Ansari *, Avinash Chaudhary, Pravin Wakte, Sachin Bhusari

University Department of Chemical Technology, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad, Maharashtra, INDIA.

Email: ansari.irfanaamer@gmail.com, chemtech.cdmpk@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The aim of present study is to develop Darunavir pro-liposome powder for oral delivery. Darunavir-loaded oral pro-liposome powder (OPP) was prepared by a solvent evaporation technique with varying independent variables at three different levels. Based on different levels pro-liposome powder formulation was optimized by using Box-Behnken design. The formulations were analyzed for its size distribution, entrapment efficiency and surface morphology. Optimized pro-liposome batch A was evaluated for physical parameter, morphological parameters, entrapment efficiency, followed by in vitro, ex- vivo and in-vivo studies. Oral pro-liposome powder showed good micromeritic properties with angle of repose was less than 30°, Carr's index and Hausner's ratio were also less than 21 and 1.25, respectively. The mean size of the vesicles was in the range of 180 to 290 nm. The assay and entrapment efficiency of pro-liposome powder formulations were $79.00 \pm 0.2\%$ and $93.46 \pm 0.2\%$ respectively. In vitro release of Darunavir pro-liposome powder was $78.17 \pm 0.1\%$ after 24 hrs which shows good release from the vesicle of pro-liposome. Ex vivo permeation study shows 58.11% enhancement which shows good permeation. The optimize batch A of pro-liposome powder indicated 50% enhancement in the relative bioavailability as compared to the Darunavir suspension. The results showed that pro-liposome powder containing Darunavir can efficiently deliver in to the blood stream. This drug delivery system has been designed as a novel platform for potential oral delivery of drugs having poor water solubility and high first-pass metabolism.

KEYWORDS: Darunavir, bioavailability, permeation, phosphatidylcholine, Box-Behnken design.

How to cite this Abstract:

Irfan Ansari, Avinash Chaudhary, Pravin Wakte, Sachin Bhusari. DEVELOPMENT OF DARUNAVIR PRO-LIPOSOME POWDER FOR ORAL DELIVERY BY USING BOX-BHENKEN DESIGN: A POTENTIAL APPROACH FOR DELIVERY OF DRUGS HAVING HIGH FIRST-PASS METABOLISM. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-3.

CRIHS-CEU-004

DEVELOPMENT & EVALUATION OF MATRIX TYPE SUSTAINED RELEASE TABLET OF LAMIVUDINE BY USING NATURAL POLYMERS

Mahesh Rindhe*, Avinash Chaudhary, Pravin Wakte, Sachin Bhusari

University Department of Chemical Technology, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad, Maharashtra, INDIA.

Email: chemtech.cdmpk@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The aim of present study was to develop and evaluate the matrix type sustained release tablet of Lamivudine by using different natural polymers. The matrix type sustained release tablets of Lamivudine were formulated using fenugreek polymer, gum tragacanth and gaur gum by wet granulation method. The three factor two level Box-Behnken design was selected for formulation development. The Lamivudine tablet was evaluated for its hardness, friability test, wet variation test and drug content test. Effect of hardness of tablet, binder concentration (fenugreek polymer, gum tragacanth and gaur gum) and polymer concentration (HPMC k 100M) on the time required to release 35% of drug (t_{35}) and percent release of drug was studied. Optimized batch of fenugreek polymer was predicted by software (Design Expert). The optimized batch (SSBF-OB) has given t_{35} up to 8.9 hrs and 97.09% drug release in a sustained way up to 24hrs. The comparative release potential of all the polymers was studied. In-vitro release data demonstrated that tablet with fenugreek polymer were successfully sustained the release of drug (97.09) up to 24 hrs as compare to the tablet with gum tragacanth (77.63%) and gaur gum (72.96%). Lamivudine tablet formulation by design of experiment showed that fenugreek based polymer has a potential to act as release rate modifier.

KEYWORDS: Fenugreek polymer, Lamivudine, Wet granulation, HPMC, Gum tragacanth.

How to cite this Abstract:

Mahesh Rindhe, Avinash Chaudhary, Pravin Wakte, Sachin Bhusari. DEVELOPMENT & EVALUATION OF MATRIX TYPE SUSTAINED RELEASE TABLET OF LAMIVUDINE BY USING NATURAL POLYMERS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-4.

CRIHS-CEU-005

PHARMACEUTICAL MANAGEMENT - 3D PRINTING OF TABLET MANUFACTURING

Madasu Susmitha and Surekuchi Uma Sukerthi

SIMS College of Pharmacy, Mangaldas Nagar, Guntur-522001, INDIA.

Email: sukeerthi2305@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The main objective of the present study was Innovation in pharmaceutical manufacturing of tablets with 3D printing. 3D printing is a form of additive manufacturing technology. To be called an innovation an idea must be replicable at an economical cost & must satisfy a specific need innovation involves deliberate application of Information, imagination, initiative, in delivering greater different values from resources & includes all processes by which new ideas are generated & converted into useful products. Drug innovation as a business process requires organizational & managerial decisions it is already enjoying intensive research coverage their mechanism driving drug discovery and development. A 3D printer is a type of industrial robot can be of almost any shape & are produced from electronic data source. 3D printing is revolutionizing pharma by allowing new substance to be tested directly on human tissues, & by changing the economics of scale, any drug cost effective.

KEYWORDS: 3D Printing, Drug innovation, Pharmaceutical management.

How to cite this Abstract:

Madasu Susmitha and Surekuchi Uma Sukerthi. PHARMACEUTICAL MANAGEMENT - 3D PRINTING OF TABLET MANUFACTURING. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-5.

CRIHS-CEU-006

DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF IN-SITU GEL FOR NASAL DELIVERY OF ANTI-MIGRAINE DRUG IN COMBINATION WITH ANTI-EMETIC DRUG

Swezel Pereira *, Pankaj Gajare, Sandesh Somnache, Riya R. Lotlikar

PES's Rajaram and Tarabai Bandekar College of Pharmacy, Farmagudi, Ponda, Goa, INDIA.

Email: swezelpereira@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to develop and characterize in-situ nasal formulation of Sumatriptan succinate and Metoclopramide hydrochloride in combination to prolong the residence time in the nasal cavity and improve the bioavailability of the drugs used. FT-IR studies revealed that there were no interactions between Sumatriptan succinate and Metoclopramide hydrochloride and in combination with various excipients. Total eight formulations of intranasal in-situ gels were prepared by "Cold Method" and subjected to evaluation for appearance, texture, viscosity, pH, gel strength, gelation temperature, drug content in-vitro and ex-vivo drug diffusion study. Drug content, in-vitro and ex-vivo drug diffusion study were evaluated by Simultaneous Estimation Method. SMP8 formulation was considered as the best formulations as it released percent cumulative drug release of 96.803 ± 0.0015 and 92.569 ± 0.0028 of Sumatriptan succinate and Metoclopramide hydrochloride respectively and obeyed Higuchi Model Kinetics. The in-vitro and ex-vivo diffusion experiments demonstrated that the intranasal in-situ gel SMP8 represents a suitable dosage form to release Sumatriptan succinate and Metoclopramide hydrochloride for 9 hours and is considered as the best formulation.

KEYWORDS: Sumatriptan succinate, Metoclopramide hydrochloride, Intranasal in-situ gels.

How to cite this Abstract:

Swezel Pereira, Pankaj Gajare, Sandesh Somnache, Riya R. Lotlikar. DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF IN-SITU GEL FOR NASAL DELIVERY OF ANTI-MIGRAINE DRUG IN COMBINATION WITH ANTI-EMETIC DRUG. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-6.

CRIHS-CEU-007

DESIGN, DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTERIZATION OF DRUG LOADED PULSINCAP DEVICE FOR THE TREATMENT OF AMOEBIASIS

Dipika Rama Gawade, Pankaj Gajare, Sandesh Somnache, Shreya Naik *

PES's Rajaram and Tarabai Bandekar College of Pharmacy, Farmagudi, Ponda, Goa, INDIA.

Email: shreyaaanaik@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

The aim of the study was to develop and evaluate pulsincap formulation of Tinidazole for colon targeted delivery. Formaldehyde treated capsule bodies were used for the preparation of pulsincaps. It was sealed with unhardened cap of the capsule. The pulsincap was formulated with the appropriate concentration of croscarmellose and drug mixture loaded in and separated by hydrogel. Hydrogel plug was prepared by direct compression method of different concentration of hydrophilic and hydrophobic polymers to obtain the desired degree of swelling. FTIR study confirms that there was no interaction observed between Tinidazole and polymers. The swelling study was carried out by using three different buffer solutions and found in the range of 190.54 to 293.76%. The drug content for all formulation was found in the range of 97.37 to 100.82%. The pulsincap was evaluated for in vitro dissolution studies and release kinetics. In- vitro release studies revealed that formulation F2 released the drug in desired time dependent drug release pattern as it release the drug 99% after 6hrs and follow first order kinetics and hence was considered as the best formulation of Tinidazole among the other formulations.

KEYWORDS: Tinidazole, Pulsincap, PDDS, hydrogel plug, swelling index.

How to cite this Abstract:

Dipika Rama Gawade, Pankaj Gajare, Sandesh Somnache, Shreya Naik. DESIGN, DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTERIZATION OF DRUG LOADED PULSINCAP DEVICE FOR THE TREATMENT OF AMOEBIASIS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-7.

CRIHS-CEU-008

DESIGN, DEVELOPMENT AND OPTIMIZATION OF LIPOSOMES FOR PULMONARY DRUG DELIVERY OF ISONIAZID

Ankita A. Poy Raiturcar *, Pankaj Gajare, Sandesh Somnache, Neha Narayan Audi

PES's Rajaram and Tarabai Bandekar College of Pharmacy, Ponda, Goa, INDIA.

Email: raiturcarankita@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to formulate liposomes loaded with an Anti-Tubercular drug; Isonicotinic Acid Hydrazide. Isoniazid is the first line drug in treatment of Pulmonary Tuberculosis belonging to BCS class III having high solubility and low permeability. The liposomes were prepared by high speed homogenization method using Cholesterol, Phosphatidyl Choline, Span 80 as lipids and surfactants respectively. Different batches of liposomes were developed by factorial design and evaluated for entrapment efficiency and drug content. The optimized batch was further evaluated for zeta potential, particle size, in-vitro dissolution, P-XRD, DTA, FTIR and SEM analysis. The characterization study revealed that the optimized formulation F₄ was having percentage entrapment efficiency 75.53%, percentage drug content 81.18%, average particle size of 241.6nm and zeta potential of -20mV. Hence promising drug delivery vehicles in the form of liposomes have been developed to increase bioavailability of Isoniazid.

KEYWORDS: Pulmonary Tuberculosis, Isoniazid, Liposomes, High speed Homogenization, Zeta potential.

How to cite this Abstract:

Ankita A. Poy Raiturcar, Pankaj Gajare, Sandesh Somnache, Neha Narayan Audi. DESIGN, DEVELOPMENT AND OPTIMIZATION OF LIPOSOMES FOR PULMONARY DRUG DELIVERY OF ISONIAZID. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-8.

CRIHS-CEU-009

DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF GASTRORETENTIVE FLOATING DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM OF HAEMATINIC AGENT

Anisha R. Naik *, Pankaj Gajare, Sandesh Somnache, Shivani Santhosh Nagarsekar

PES's Rajaram and Tarabai Bandekar College of Pharmacy, Ponda, Goa, INDIA.

Email: naikanisha166@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The purpose of present study was to prepare Gastroretentive floating tablet of Ferrous Gluconate to prolong the gastric residence time and to improve bioavailability in the treatment of iron deficiency anemia. Formulations were prepared using direct compression method using HPMC K4M and HPMC K100M polymers. The formulation were evaluated for physical parameters like thickness, hardness, friability, uniformity of weight, drug content, buoyancy time, **in-vitro** dissolution, and drug release mechanism. FTIR studies revealed that there was no possible interaction between the drug and other component of the formulations. Formulation F3 was found to be the best formulation compared to other formulations as it released 97.78% cumulative drug release at the end of 6th hour and followed the zero order mechanism for drug release with buoyancy time of 6 hours, drug content 101.1% and swelling index 219.8%.

KEYWORDS: Floating tablets, Ferrous Gluconate, Anemia, Bioavailability.

How to cite this Abstract:

Anisha R. Naik, Pankaj Gajare, Sandesh Somnache, Shivani Santhosh Nagarsekar. DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF GASTRORETENTIVE FLOATING DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM OF HAEMATINIC AGENT. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-9.

CRIHS-CEU-010

CERAMOSIDES AS ORAL MOISTURIZERS

Dr. S. Naazneen

Assistant Professor, St. Mary's College of Pharmacy, Secunderabad, Telangana, INDIA.

Email: umenaaz@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

Skin consists of three distinct layers viz. epidermis, dermis and hypodermis. The major barrier resides within the exterior layers of the epidermis which are sloughed off and repopulated from these inner cells of stratum corneum, granulosum, spinosum and basale. Stratum corneum helps lock the moisture within the skin as well as protects from external influences and maintains the skin equilibrium. By virtue of this unique engineering skin can provide protection against desiccation as well as invasions. Ceramides, which comprise the major constituents (about 50%) of the free extractable stratum corneum lipids majorly help in structuring and maintaining the epidermal barrier function of human skin. Their concentrations are lowered in the stratum corneum of atopic dermatitis, dry skin and in ageing causing reduced structural integrity. Oral moisturizers contain glucosyl ceramide and digalactosyl diglycerides (DGCG) complex along with phospholipids and triglycerides. After oral ingestion, glucosyl ceramides undergo metabolism by ceramidase in the GI tract forming sphingosine and free fatty acid. These sphingosine then reassemble to form ceramides in the epidermis. In vivo studies supports and ensures that the ceramides as oral moisturiser's components reach the skin where they participate in the synthesis of new ceramides. Orally ceramides reduce transepidermal water loss, increase skin moisturization, increase skin elasticity. Skin hydration is a critical element in the treatment for many dermal conditions. Oral moisturizers are a leap ahead in the endeavour of achieving the skin homeostasis. Oral treatment further improves patient compliance and it holds a chance to change the face of the current standard of care.

KEYWORDS: Skin, Oral Moisturisers, Ceramides.

How to cite this Abstract:

Dr. S. Naazneen. CERAMOSIDES AS ORAL MOISTURIZERS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-10.

CRIHS-CEU-011

MODIFIED CO-POLYMER WITH DUAL RESPONSIVE ACTIVITY FOR ANTI-CANCER DRUG DELIVERY

Riya A. Hegde *, Dr. Archana Patil

KLE college of Pharmacy, JNMC Campus, Nehru Nagar, Belagavi,
Karnataka - 590010, INDIA.

Email: riyahegde7@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The present study aimed to synthesize the co-polymer alginate-g-poly(N-isopropylacrylamide) (ALG-g-PNIPAAm) by two methods namely dispersion copolymerization method and radical free polymerization method and evaluate its dual responsiveness to be used as a carrier for anticancer drug delivery. The main purpose of this study was to target the drug moiety directly to the affected organ, tissue or cells. For this, the co-polymer was synthesized and its base structure as well as lower critical solution temperature (LCST) was determined. Capecitabine was then loaded efficiently into the synthesized co-polymer by using ultrasonic probe sonicator to prepare nanoparticles and the nanoparticles were evaluated for their physicochemical properties i.e particle size, PDI, loading efficiency and in vitro drug release. The morphological study showed that Capecitabine loaded nanoparticles was spherical and uniform in size. The loading efficiency was found to be in the range of 90%-97.6% respectively. The in vitro stimuli triggered drug release study showed the higher percent drug release at acidic pH (6.8) and higher temperature (35±0.5 °C) as compared to alkaline pH 7.4 and temperature 37±0.5°C. In conclusion, the developed Nano particulate system is an effective dual responsive carrier which can be efficiently used for Capecitabine delivery after proper optimization to achieve targeted drug delivery.

KEYWORDS: Capecitabine, Alginate, Poly (N-isopropylacrylamide), pH and Temperature responsive co-polymer.

How to cite this Abstract:

Riya A. Hegde, Dr. Archana Patil. MODIFIED CO-POLYMER WITH DUAL RESPONSIVE ACTIVITY FOR ANTI-CANCER DRUG DELIVERY. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-11.

CRIHS-CEU-012

DEVELOPMENT AND *IN VITRO* EVALUATION OF SITAGLIPTIN MUCOADHESIVE TABLETS FOR NIDDM

B. Nagarani ^a*, Dr. G.V. Radha ^a, Santhosh Kumar Chinnaiyan ^b

^a Department of Pharmaceutics, Srikrupa Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Velikatta, Kondapak, Siddipet, Telangana State - 502277, INDIA.

^b Department of Pharmaceutics, GITAM (deemed to be) University, Rushikonda, Visakapatnam - 530045, Andhra Pradesh, INDIA.

ABSTRACT

The objective of the present work was to develop an oral Mucoadhesive Sitagliptin tablet for the sustained-release. Sitagliptin a biguanide, has a relatively short plasma half-life and low absolute bioavailability. The tablets were prepared by the Wet Granulation method, using biodegradable mucoadhesive polymer Xanthan gum and pectin at different concentrations. All the batches were evaluated for thickness, weight variation, hardness, drug content uniformity, in vitro drug release, and mucoadhesion strength. Mean dissolution time is used to characterize the drug release rate from a dosage form, and indicates the drug release-retarding efficiency of the polymer. The in vitro studies the formulations containing Pectin showed less retardation than the formulation with Xanthan gum. The Sitagliptin release effectively controlled for 12 h with Xanthan gum, thus, can be successfully employed for formulating mucoadhesive tablets. Fitting the data to the Zero order and Higuchi equation indicated the mechanism of drug release. The study reveals that Xanthan gum highest mucoadhesive strength compared with pectin.

KEYWORDS: Sitagliptin, Xanthan gum, Pectin, Mucoadhesive tablets.

How to cite this Abstract:

B. Nagarani, Dr. G.V. Radha, Santhosh Kumar Chinnaiyan. DEVELOPMENT AND *IN VITRO* EVALUATION OF SITAGLIPTIN MUCOADHESIVE TABLETS FOR NIDDM. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-12.

CRIHS-CEU-013

DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF ORAL DOSAGE FORMULATIONS OF AN ANTIEMETIC DRUG USING NATURAL CARRIERS

Aishwarya Parvatkar *, Shilpa Bhilegaonkar, Anushka Prabhu Parrikar

Department of Pharmaceutics, P.E.S's Rajaram and Tarabai Bandekar College of Pharmacy, Farmagudi, Ponda, Goa, INDIA.

ABSTRACT

*Ondansetron is a competitive serotonin type 3 receptor antagonist which is widely used in the treatment of chemotherapy, radiation therapy and surgery induced nausea and vomiting. The current marketed formulations available are injectable solutions, tablets, oral solutions, oral soluble films and orally disintegrating tablets. The purpose of the present research work was to formulate mouth releasing formulations of Ondansetron hydrochloride by masking its bitter taste using natural carriers which could be consumed without water during travelling. Two different dosage forms were formulated which included mouth releasing pills and lyophilized powder for subsequent compression using natural excipients such as *Abelmoschus esculentus* extract and sago pearls. Such approaches would be preferred over synthetically processed formulations as they are safe and biocompatible. The mouth releasing pills were evaluated for appearance, hardness, friability, weight variation, disintegration time, drug content and in vitro drug release studies. The lyophilized powder was evaluated for various pre compression like bulk density, tapped density, angle of repose, Carr's index, Hausner's ratio and post compression parameters like drug content and in vitro drug release studies. The approaches were found to be acceptable in terms of physicochemical performance but release pattern was required to be modified by carrying out further studies.*

KEYWORDS: *Ondansetron hydrochloride, Abelmoschus esculentus, Sago pearls, Mouth releasing.*

How to cite this Abstract:

Aishwarya Parvatkar, Shilpa Bhilegaonkar, Anushka Prabhu Parrikar. DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF ORAL DOSAGE FORMULATIONS OF AN ANTIEMETIC DRUG USING NATURAL CARRIERS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-13.

CRIHS-CEU-014

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF ELEUSINE CORACANA EDIBLE MEDICATED JELLIES FOR THE DELIVERY OF PARACETAMOL

Punita Naik *, Shilpa Bhilegaonkar, Huzefa Ujjainwala

Department of Pharmaceutics, P.E.S's Rajaram and Tarabai Bandekar College of Pharmacy Farmagudi, Ponda, Goa, INDIA.

ABSTRACT

*F*ever is a series of biological effects produced by endotoxin and pyrogen. The purpose of this study is to formulate innovative product of paracetamol which is the drug of choice in treating fever. Jellies are semisolid dosage forms and can be used internally as well as externally. Advantages of this formulation is that it does not require water for ingestion possesses aesthetic appearance and good texture. In this study a natural and novel gel base was used that is Eleusine coracana (ragi). The Eleusine coracana slurry was made using Eleusine coracana seeds and then mixed with other ingredients and the jellies were formulated. The prepared jellies were then evaluated for physical examination, pH, weight variation, syneresis, drug content, in vitro dissolution and stability studies. The formulated jellies complied with the requirements and were found to be better than the conventional dosage form and are accepted by children.

KEYWORDS: Paracetamol, Eleusine coracana, semisolid, Medicated jelly.

How to cite this Abstract:

Punita Naik, Shilpa Bhilegaonkar, Huzefa Ujjainwala. FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF ELEUSINE CORACANA EDIBLE MEDICATED JELLIES FOR THE DELIVERY OF PARACETAMOL. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-14.

CRIHS-CEU-015

DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF NOVEL TRANSUNGUAL PATCH FOR THE TREATMENT OF ONYCHOMICOSIS

Ankita Bhangui *, Shilpa Bhilegaonkar, Purva Laad

Department of Pharmaceutics, P.E.S's Rajaram and Tarabai Bandekar College of Pharmacy, Farmagudi, Ponda, Goa – 403401, INDIA.

ABSTRACT

Transungual therapy is desirable in the treatment of Onychomycosis (fungal infection of the nail) since it involves drug delivery through the nail plate. In order to improve residence time of the drug with the nail. Different formulations of patches of Sertaconazole nitrate were prepared. The backing membrane and reservoir layer were prepared by using polymers like Ethyl Cellulose, Polymethyl metacrylate (PMMA) and Chitosan. And drug in Self Microemulsifying Drug Delivery system (SMEDDs) was also prepared. The patch was evaluated for thickness, weight variation, drug content, folding endurance, moisture content, moisture uptake and in-vitro release study. Data of in-vitro release was fitted into various kinetic models to explain the mechanism of drug release. The selected formulations from both the approaches were subjected to accelerated stability testing according to ICH guidelines and were found to be stable.

KEYWORDS: Onychomycosis, Transungual Patch, Sertaconazole, Self Microemulsifying.

How to cite this Abstract:

Ankita Bhangui, Shilpa Bhilegaonkar, Purva Laad. DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF NOVEL TRANSUNGUAL PATCH FOR THE TREATMENT OF ONYCHOMICOSIS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-15.

CRIHS-CEU-016

LEPIDIUM SATIVUM AS A NOVEL POLYMER FOR SUSTAINED RELEASE SYSTEMS

Swana Dias *, Shilpa Bhilegaonkar, Vaibhavi Prabhugaonkar

Department of Pharmaceutics, P.E.S's Rajaram and Tarabai Bandekar college of Pharmacy, Farmagudi, Ponda, Goa - 403401, INDIA.

ABSTRACT

Natural excipients have many advantages over the ones that are synthetically processed because of better patient compliance, cost effectiveness, less processing steps and are environmental friendly. Lepidium Sativum is used as a novel polymer in the manufacturing of pharmaceutical solid oral dosage forms. The most frequently used controlled release oral dosage forms are the matrix tablets. Hydrophilic matrices are prepared by direct compression of a powder mixture of the drug with a release retardant and other additives. Such materials have advantages associated with their manufacturing eg-simple formulation, use of existing tableting technology and low cost of polymers. In the hydrophilic matrix the drug is entrapped in the polymer matrix, therefore it has the ability to release the drug over a defined period of time. Hydrophobic matrix systems are formulated by using waxes and are suitable for drugs with high solubility. Even though hydrophobic matrices can modulate drug release, the processes such as hot fusion and thermal treatment increases the length of processes in tablet manufacturing. The properties of Lepidium Sativum as a polymer matrix with hydrophilic and hydrophobic drugs were checked and then compared with standard matricing agent Hydroxy Propyl Methyl Cellulose (HPMC). Cefixime trihydrate and Amoxicillin trihydrate were selected as model drugs on which studies were carried out.

KEYWORDS: *Lepidium Sativum, Novel Polymer, Hydrophilic Matrix, Hydrophobic Matrix, Sustained Release.*

How to cite this Abstract:

Swana Dias, Shilpa Bhilegaonkar, Vaibhavi Prabhugaonkar. LEPIDIUM SATIVUM AS A NOVEL POLYMER FOR SUSTAINED RELEASE SYSTEMS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-16.

CRIHS-CEU-017

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF A DENTAL GEL CONTAINING THE ACTIVE PRINCIPLE'S OF *MIMUSOPS ELENGI* AGAINST ORAL PATHOGENS

Gunda Mahesh ^{1*}, Dr. V. Gopal ²

¹ PhD Research scholar, MTPG & RIHS, Pondicherry University, Pondicherry, INDIA.

² Principal College of Pharmacy, MTPG & RIHS, Pondicherry, INDIA.

Email: maheshpharma6@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The objective of the study is to formulate and evaluate a dental gel containing the Mimusops elengi bark extract for anti microbial activity. Six herbal gel formulations were prepared using propylene glycol, carbomers, triethyl amine as gelling agents and were evaluated for physical appearance, net content, viscosity, Extrudability, pH, Spreadability and In-vitro diffusion profile and primary skin irritation tests the stability study for the dental herbal gel formulation was done as per ICH guide lines and In-vitro anti microbial activity was evaluated by agar well diffusion method. Skin irritation test conforming the gel was non toxic and safe. From In-vitro anti microbial activity results dental gel formulation showing good effect.

KEYWORDS: *Mimusops elengi, Anti microbial activity, Dental gel.*

How to cite this Abstract:

Gunda Mahesh, Dr. V. Gopal. FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF A DENTAL GEL CONTAINING THE ACTIVE PRINCIPLE'S OF *MIMUSOPS ELENGI* AGAINST ORAL PATHOGENS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-17.

CRIHS-CEU-018

DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF MULTIFUNCTIONAL NATURAL POLYMER FROM SEEDS OF *DELONIX REGIA*

Tejal Chaudhari *, Avinash Chaudhary, Pravin Wakte, Sachin Bhusari

University Department of Chemical Technology, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad, Maharashtra, INDIA.

Email: chemtech.cdmpk@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study covers development of multifunctional polymer compound which has tremendous effect on hemorrhage and it could be used as potential sustained release polymer in the pharmaceutical formulations also. External 'Hemorrhage' has been foremost cause of death among disasters, war-prone areas and accidental cases. According to World Health Organization more than 1.2 million people die in accident and about more than 50 million populations are injured each year. Thus, it becomes imperative to develop new polymer having multifunctional properties that can be act as anti-hemorrhage. The polymer was developed by using precipitation methodology. The macerate of seeds of Delonix regia was prepared, centrifuge and supernatant was separated. Precipitation solvent like acetone was added in supernatant. The ratio of solvent and supernatant was 1:3 give more precipitation as compared to the other ratios taken for the study. In -vitro and In- vivo studies showed that, this polymer was capable of inducing the formation of robust clot within 2 min. In present study, we attempted to design polymer with effective hemostatic property. Another property of polymer is to act as release modifier in the formulation for that, sustained release tablet of metoprolol tartrate was formulated and evaluated for its sustained release property. Form the In-vitro release study of tablet it was observed that, it has capability to sustained the release of metoprolol tartrate. The 90% of metoprolol tartrate was release from the matrix up to 24 hrs.

KEYWORDS: *Delonix regia, Polymer, Hemorrhage, Metoprolol tartrate.*

How to cite this Abstract:

Tejal Chaudhari, Avinash Chaudhary, Pravin Wakte, Sachin Bhusari. DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF MULTIFUNCTIONAL NATURAL POLYMER FROM SEEDS OF *DELONIX REGIA*. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-18.

CRIHS-CEU-019

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF MICROSPONGE BASED ORNIDAZOLE SUSTAINED RELEASE TABLET

Bharti Gotmare *, Avinash Chaudhary, Pravin Wakte, Sachin Bhusari

University Department of Chemical Technology, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad,
Maharashtra, INDIA.

Email: chemtech.cdmpk@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The aim of present study is to develop topical formulation that release Ornidazole in sustained manner with less side effects and gives better efficacy in the form of microsponges delivery system. Microsponges loaded with Ornidazole was prepared by using quasi-emulsion solvent diffusion method. The Microsponges formulations were prepared with three different amounts of Eudragit RS 100 polymer and Propylene glycol. Total nine batches of Ornidazole Microsponges were formulated (ONZ-MS 1 to ONZ-MS 9) and evaluated for its microscopic properties, particle size analysis, production yield, entrapment efficiency, compatibility study of drug with excipient was studied using FT-IR, surface morphology was studied using Scanning Electron Microscopy, In-vitro release study, stability studies on different temp condition ($4 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, $25 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and $45 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$) for 3 months were carried out. Ornidazole Microsponges (ONZ-MS 9) was found to be stable at 25°C to 45°C and it was further evaluated for its different parameters. The production yield was increased (78.36%) with increased in the entrapment (92.48%) and efficacy of ONZ-MS 9. The optimized ONZ-MS 9 batch was compressed into tablet by using direct compression method. The different diluents like microcrystalline cellulose, lactose was used to prepared directly compressible Ornidazole Microsponges tablets. These ONZ Microsponges tablets were evaluated for its hardness, thickness, drug content, friability and In-vitro release study. The Ornidazole Microsponges tablets showed better release profile up to 12 hrs.

KEYWORDS: Ornidazole, Microsponges, Eudragit RS 100, In-vitro release.

How to cite this Abstract:

Bharti Gotmare, Avinash Chaudhary, Pravin Wakte, Sachin Bhusari. FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF MICROSPONGE BASED ORNIDAZOLE SUSTAINED RELEASE TABLET. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-19.

CRIHS-CEU-020

PILL CAMERA: NEW EMERGING TREND IN DIAGNOSIS

Hashweta Gawde *, Shilpa Bhilegaonka, Ankita Bhangui

Department of Pharmaceutics, P.E.S's Rajaram & Tarabai Bandekar College of Pharmacy, Farmagudi, Ponda, Goa – 403401, INDIA.

ABSTRACT

Endoscopy is a non surgical procedure used to examine a person's digestive tract using an endoscope, a flexible tube with a light and camera attached to it. Your doctor can view the pictures of your digestive tract on a TV monitor. Though it is useful, the technique is very painful where to overcome this disadvantage new emerging technology has invented Pill Camera. The aim of technology is to make products in a large scale for cheaper price and increased quality. The Pill Camera is the recent advancement in the field of technology. The conventional method used was Endoscopy. The Pill Camera is the size of a multivitamin capsule and is swallowed with a sip of water. The Pill Camera is made up of bio-compatible material which is resistant to stomach acid. The Pill Camera helps in detecting Ulcers, Crohn's Disease, Polyps, Cancer and tumors of the small intestine. The main advantage of Pill Camera Over conventional endoscopy or colonoscopy is that it helps in the examination of small intestine which was not possible by conventional method. The present poster will focus on describing components, fabrication, working and uses of Pill Camera in the field of diagnosis.

KEYWORDS: Pill Camera, Endoscopy.

How to cite this Abstract:

Hashweta Gawde, Shilpa Bhilegaonka, Ankita Bhangui. PILL CAMERA: NEW EMERGING TREND IN DIAGNOSIS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-20.

CRIHS-CEU-021

RECENT ADVANCES IN COATING TECHNOLOGY

Marfa Sheikh *, Shilpa Bhilegaonkar, Aishwarya Katkar

Department of Pharmaceutics, P.E.S's Rajaram & Tarabai Bandekar College of Pharmacy, Farmagudi, Ponda, Goa – 403401, INDIA.

ABSTRACT

Coating is a process by which a thin polymeric film is applied to surface of dosage form in order to confer specific benefits that broadly ranges from facilitating product identification, to improve stability, to mask bitter taste of the drug, to modify drug release from dosage form and so on. Traditional method of coating involves making the polymeric dispersion in suitable solvent and spraying on substrate. There are various techniques for tablet coating such as sugar coating, film coating and enteric coating. The amount of coating on the surface of the tablet is critical to the effectiveness of the oral dosage form. Recent trends in Pharmaceutical technologies are towards the development of coating methods which are overcome the various disadvantages associated with solvent based coating. In these latest technologies coating materials are directly sprayed onto the solid dosage form without using any solvent and then cured by various methods to form coat hence these methods are sometimes called as solvent less coating. Various solvent less coating are available such as Photo curable coating, Magnetically assistant impact on coating, Compression hot melt coating, Powder coating, Electrostatic dry coating, Supercritical fluid coating. This poster summaries the fundamental principles, recent tablet coating and remedies associated with tablet coating.

KEYWORDS: Polymeric Dispersion, Coating Techniques, Solvent Less Coating.

How to cite this Abstract:

Marfa Sheikh, Shilpa Bhilegaonkar, Aishwarya Katkar. RECENT ADVANCES IN COATING TECHNOLOGY. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-21.

CRIHS-CEU-022

A REVIEW ON ROBOTS IN PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRY; A TOOL TO INCREASE PRODUCTIVITY

Swati Yearimani *, Shilpa Bhilegaonkar, Swana Dias

Department of Pharmaceutics, P.E.S's Rajaram & Tarabai Bandekar College of Pharmacy, Farmagudi, Ponda, Goa – 403401, INDIA.

ABSTRACT

The Science, Technology, Design, Manufacture and Application of robotics in the pharmaceutical industry.

There are more than 1,50,000 robots that have been installed over the world and are mostly utilized in the pharmaceutical industry. Robotics is used to assemble and package a variety of medical devices including implants, they are also employed for doing assay analysis and automating the most of test tubes in research laboratories. Robots improve the safety and productivity of workers. These robotic products are designed specifically for the industry. Robots play an important role in high throughput screening. Laboratory robotics is used for developing new experimental procedure. However robotic manufacture has multiple challenges in developing these products. The present poster will highlight various types, working, controlling and all of the robots in the pharmaceutical industry.

KEYWORDS: Robotics, Pharmaceutical application, screening.

How to cite this Abstract:

Swati Yearimani, Shilpa Bhilegaonkar, Swana Dias. A REVIEW ON ROBOTS IN PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRY; A TOOL TO INCREASE PRODUCTIVITY. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-22.

CRIHS-CEU-023

AUTOMATION AND DIGITALIZATION IN PHARMACEUTICALS

Yashodita Desai *, Shilpa Bhilegaonkar, Punita Naik

Department of Pharmaceutics, P.E.S's Rajaram and Tarabai Bandekar College of Pharmacy, Farmagudi, Ponda, Goa - 403401, INDIA.

Email: aishwaryakatkar05@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The rapid progress in the pharmaceutical industry is due to advancement in the digitalization and automation starting from invention to the administration of drug. Every advancement in the development of a pharmaceutical product is associated with progress in digitalization. A drug or a drug product to be administered safely and provide efficacy it has to undergo a long journey from its discovery including preclinical and clinical trials to further product development. The quality control and quality assurance systems utilize digitalization to maintain the details of manufacturing processes, the quality and standard of the drug product. Packaging and labelling of the drug product are carried out with effective automation. Therefore, the present poster shall review on various techniques for digitalization and automation such as: During drug development – NMR, during clinical trials – EDC, for filing of new drug application – eCTD, for research and development – F-CAD, for production and manufacturing – CIM and CAM, for quality control and quality assurance – QRM and QBD, for packaging and labelling – RFID, for sales and marketing – EBR, for dispensing pharmacy – eRx, for drug monitoring – eDMS and PDMPs.

KEYWORDS: Automation, Digitalization, Pharmaceutical Industry, Computer aided design, RFID.

How to cite this Abstract:

Yashodita Desai, Shilpa Bhilegaonkar, Punita Naik. AUTOMATION AND DIGITALIZATION IN PHARMACEUTICALS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-23.

CRIHS-CEU-024

**DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF MODIFIED RELEASE SOLID ORAL DOSAGE FORM
(TOLCAPONE)**

B. Manjula *

Sree College of Pharmacy, Nayakulagudem, Kothagudem, Telangana, INDIA.

ABSTRACT

The present research work focuses on design and development of modified Release solid oral dosage form. Tolcapone: based on the assessment of various parameters, in vitro drug dissolution profile and drug kinetics, hf16 was found to be optimized formulation. The drug release from hf16 was found to fit zero order and best fitted to Higuchi's model confirming to be the diffusion assisted mechanism. FT-IR & DSC studies revealed that there was no interaction between the drug and polymers used in the formulations. In vivo bioavailability studies were conducted for optimized tolcapone trilayer tablets and marketed product, in vivo studies indicating that the optimized tolcapone formulation was shown sustained release patterns where marketed product was shown immediate release. So the optimized formulation was shown significant plasma concentrations with sustained release and maintained for 24 h. Based on the mucoadhesive study, the optimized dosage form adhesive to gastro intestinal tract more than 12 hours.

KEYWORDS: Tolcapone, FT-IR, DSC, Mucoadhesive study.

How to cite this Abstract:

B. Manjula. DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF MODIFIED RELEASE SOLID ORAL DOSAGE FORM (TOLCAPONE). J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-24.

CRIHS-CEU-025

DESIGN AND CHARACTERISATION OF ACECLOFENAC MULTIPARTICULATE COLON TARGETED DRUG DELIVERY

B. Anvesh *, G. Kartheek

Sree College of Pharmacy, Nayakulagudem, Kothagudem, Telangana, INDIA.

ABSTRACT

This Present work was design and develop sconsistent and optimized formulations of aceclofenac multiparticulate targeted drug delivery to colon with the following objectives. The first purpose of the study was developing multiparticulate cdds by means of swelling and time dependent polymers such as hydroxypropyl cellulose (HPC) and ethyl cellulose (ec) embedded on aceclofenac to let loose the drug at colon in a sustained manner. The marketed product released by first order kinetics by concentration dependent. In vivo bioavailability studies were conducted for optimized formulation.

KEYWORDS: Aceclofenac, Pellets, CDDS.

How to cite this Abstract:

B. Anvesh, G. Kartheek. DESIGN AND CHARACTERISATION OF ACECLOFENAC MULTIPARTICULATE COLON TARGETED DRUG DELIVERY. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-25.

CRIHS-CEU-026

PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF EXTENDED RELEASE MATRIX TABLETS OF BISOPROLOL FUMERATE USING NATURAL AND SYNTHETIC POLYMERS

Ch. Prasanna *

Sree College of Pharmacy, Nayakulagudem, Kothagudem, Telangana, INDIA.

ABSTRACT

The aim of the present study was to develop Extended release formulation of Bisoprolol to maintain constant therapeutic levels of the drug for over 12 hrs. HPMC K15M, Ethyl cellulose, Carbopol, Manugel were employed as polymers. All the formulations were passed various physicochemical evaluation parameters and they were found to be within limits. From the dissolution studies it was evident that the formulation (F4) showed better and desired drug release pattern i.e., 98.26% in 12 hours. It contains the HPMC K15M and Ethyl Cellulose combination polymer. It followed kars mayer peppas kinetics mechanism.

KEYWORDS: Bisoprolol, HPMCK15M, Ethyl Cellulose, Carbopol 934, Manugel.

How to cite this Abstract:

Ch. Prasanna. PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF EXTENDED RELEASE MATRIX TABLETS OF BISOPROLOL FUMERATE USING NATURAL AND SYNTHETIC POLYMERS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-26.

CRIHS-CEU-027

EVALUATION OF ANALGESIC AND ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY OF *CITRUS LIMON* PEEL IN ALBINO WISTAR RATS

Ch. Sai Priya *, K.Soundarya Rani

Sree College of Pharmacy, Nayakulagudem, Kothagudem, Telangana, INDIA.

ABSTRACT

The lemon [Citrus limon (L.) Rutaceae] exhibits many important natural chemical components, including citric acid, ascorbic acid, minerals and phenolic compounds, such flavonoids. Although their biological properties have always been associated with their content of vitamin C, it has recently been shown that flavonoids and other nutrients and non-nutrients (vitamins, minerals, dietary fiber, essential oils and carotenoids). Therefore, their health-promoting effects, such as obesity, diabetes, blood lipid lowering, cardiovascular diseases, brain disorders and certain types of cancer, have been associated with their contents, especially vitamin C and flavonoids, due to their natural antioxidant characteristics. Therefore, this work was designed based on phytochemical constitution such as flavonoids in Citrus limon peel extracts because flavonoids are rich in the treatment for evaluation of analgesic and anti-inflammatory activity in rats. Fresh and cr shed peel of Citrus limon were collected and then extracted with different solvents such as water, alcohol and methanol at the doses of 100 mg/kg, 200 mg/kg body weight in experimental animal models. Analgesic activity was evaluated by Hot -plate and tail-flick method in albino wistar rats; acute and chronic anti-inflammatory activity was evaluated by carrageenan-induced paw oedema and formalin-induced paw edema in Wistar albino rats. Diclofenac sodium and indomethacin were employed as reference drugs for analgesic and anti-inflammatory studies, respectively. In the present study, the aqueous, alcoholic and methanolic extracts of Citrus limon demonstrated significant analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities in the tested models.

KEYWORDS: Citrus Limon, Hot-Plate, Tail-Flick.

How to cite this Abstract:

Ch. Sai Priya, K.Soundarya Rani. EVALUATION OF ANALGESIC AND ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY OF *CITRUS LIMON* PEEL IN ALBINO WISTAR RATS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-27.

CRIHS-CEU-028

POLYSACCHARIDE INDUCED PRODUCTION OF SILVER NANOPARTICLES (AG-NPS) AND THEIR ANTIBACTERIAL EFFICACY AGAINST SELECTED BACTERIAL PATHOGENS

Y. Sravanthi *

Sree College of Pharmacy, Nayakulagudem, Kothagudem, Telangana, INDIA.

ABSTRACT

Synthesis of silver nanoparticles (Ag -NPs) using sustainable thermo-chemical method have drawn considerable interest in the field of nanotechnology. Polysaccharides have been used as stabilizing and reducing agents for the synthesis of silver nanoparticles. In the present investigation two different sources of starch (synthetic starch, rice starch) have been used to reduce precursor of Ag ions for the rate of nucleation and size distribution of silver nanoparticles. The synthesized silver nanoparticles were adopted to characterize by UV-visible spectroscopy, field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM) analysis and antibacterial assay. The surface plasmon resonance (SPR) absorption of nanoparticles was monitored by using UV-visible spectrophotometer and maximum peaked at 440nm and 420nm respectively. The FESEM micrograph of synthetic starch mediated silver nanoparticles shows that an irregular shaped with size range of 60-100nm and natural starch mediated silver nanoparticles demonstrate that spherical shaped nanoparticles having the size range of 60-80nm. Natural starch mediated silver nanoparticles showed highest antibacterial activity (25 mm) against Shigella sp. Among the bacterial pathogens tested Gram negative bacteria are more susceptible than the Gram positive bacteria by the nanoparticle synthesized using natural starch as a reducing and stabilizing agent. Thermo-chemical mediated natural starch induced silver nanomaterials can be considered as reliable, eco-friendly and cost effective approach and evident by the properties of the nanoparticles.

KEYWORDS: Silver Nanoparticles, Polysaccharide, Starch, Fesem analysis, Antibacteria.

How to cite this Abstract:

Y. Sravanthi. POLYSACCHARIDE INDUCED PRODUCTION OF SILVER NANOPARTICLES (AG-NPS) AND THEIR ANTIBACTERIAL EFFICACY AGAINST SELECTED BACTERIAL PATHOGENS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-28.

CRIHS-CEU-029

FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF INJECTION OF POORLY SOLUBLE DRUG USING MIXED SOLVENCY CONCEPT

N. Sreeja *, B. Subash *

Sree College of Pharmacy, Nayakulagudem, Kothagudem, Telangana, INDIA.

ABSTRACT

Mixed solvency, a new concept of solubilization states that all substances whether solids, liquids or gases possess solubilizing power and hence concentrated solution containing various dissolved substances in any liquid can also improve the solubility of poorly soluble drugs. Mixed solvency technique can be employed in injection formulation of poorly soluble drugs in order to reduce concentration of individual solubilizer (used for solubility enhancement) to minimize the toxic effects of solubilizers. For example in most of the methods of aqueous solubilization, high concentration of an additive (hydrotropic agent/cosolvents/surfactants/ cyclodextrins etc.) is required to produce an appreciable increase in solubility of a poorly water soluble drug. In this case, the solubilizing agent employed to give a desirable solubility for the poorly soluble drug may produce its own toxicity. Similarly, the presence of several oil soluble additives (each in small concentration) in oil, forming a concentrated solution may enhance the oil solubility of a poorly oil soluble drug efficiently. In the present investigation, rifampicin was selected as model poorly oil soluble drug. Castor oil was used as model oil and thymol, menthol, camphor, phenol, ethanol, benzyl alcohol and oleic acid were used as model oil soluble/miscible additives. Oily injection was made as a result of oily solubility effect of these additives. The results of solubility study revealed the significance of mixed solvency and the stability studies data supports that the developed formulation using this technique gives good stability also.

KEYWORDS: Mixed solvency, Poorly Oil Soluble, Injection Formulation and Toxicity issues.

How to cite this Abstract:

N. Sreeja, B. Subash. FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF INJECTION OF POORLY SOLUBLE DRUG USING MIXED SOLVENCY CONCEPT. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-29.

CRIHS-CEU-030

ROLE OF POLYMERIC INTERACTIONS IN SOLUBILITY ENHANCEMENT OF ETODOLAC BY USING MILLING AND HOT MELT EXTRUSION TECHNIQUE

Puja Rathod *, Avinash Chaudhary, Pravin Wakte, Sachin Bhusari

University Department of Chemical Technology, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad,
Maharashtra, INDIA.

Email: chemtech.cdmpk@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The objective of present work was to study the drug-polymeric interaction to improve solubility and hence dissolution rate of poorly soluble drug Etodolac by milling and melt extrusion techniques. During milling high shear generated which increases high interfacial area of drug and polymer promotes amorphous powder formation. However in melt extrusion, high shear mixing of the molten mass cause dispersion of the drug and the polymer at molecular level with drug-polymer interactions promotes amorphization. Etodolac is weak acid with poor water solubility. The polymers selected for study were Copovidone (Kollidon® VA64) and Eudragit EPO (cationic). Ball mill was used for milling amorphization whereas, single screw Hot Melt Extruder (HME) was used for fusion amorphization. The formulation optimized for drug polymer weight ratio, milling time, Screw speed of (HME), HME temperature. In-vitro dissolution rate of Etodolac formulation is improved in pH 1.2 buffer solution as compared to that of the pure drug and physical mixtures. The amorphous material was characterized for Crystallinity (DSC and XRD), Drug polymeric interaction study and drug chemical stability (FTIR). Extrusion was found efficient technique for carrier based amorphization as compared to ball mill. Hot melt extruder parameter optimized in order to form uniform molecular level dispersion (Screw speed 50 rpm and temperature 120°C). Extruded product of Etodolac and Eudragit EPO has shown significant enhancement in dissolution. DSC and XRD study shows loss in crystallinity and reveals amorphization of drug. Drug-polymeric interaction confirmed by FTIR analysis.

KEYWORD: Etodolac, Milling and Melt extrusion techniques, FT-IR, DSC, XRD.

How to cite this Abstract:

Puja Rathod, Avinash Chaudhary, Pravin Wakte, Sachin Bhusari. ROLE OF POLYMERIC INTERACTIONS IN SOLUBILITY ENHANCEMENT OF ETODOLAC BY USING MILLING AND HOT MELT EXTRUSION TECHNIQUE. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-30.

CRIHS-CEU-031

PROLIPOSOME BASED TRANSDERMAL DELIVERY OF KETOCONAZOLE

Rajendra Prasad R *, Pavani U and Rajkumar V

Chaitanya College of Pharmacy Education and Research, Kishanpura, Hanamkonda, T.S - 506001, INDIA.

Email: prasad.chinna225@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

Ketoconazole (KTZ), an antifungal agent which undergoes extensive first pass metabolism and used in treatment of various fungal infections. KTZ was developed into proliposomes for transdermal delivery which provides sustained and localised action. The proliposomal gel was prepared by using modified coacervation phase separation method by using different ratios of lecithin and cholesterol. The prepared proliposomes were characterized for size, zeta potential and entrapment efficiency were in the range of 401 to 724nm, -8.5 to -17.4mV and 81 – 94% respectively. The *in vitro* release data was fitted into different mathematical models which suggest that, it follows zero order kinetics with diffusion mechanism. The permeation assessed in terms of permeation parameters (flux, permeability coefficient, and enhancement ratio) were calculated. The higher deposition of KTZ in skin layers with proliposome gel (F3) compared with control and marketed cream reveals that potential of this formulation in avoiding the barrier function of the SC and delivering the drug efficiently into the viable regions of the skin. The optimized formulation was further characterized for skin irritation study, DSC, histopathology of the skin and stability. The stability data reveal that the formulations stored at 4°C are stable compared to formulation stored at room temperature.

How to cite this Abstract:

Rajendra Prasad R, Pavani U and Rajkumar V. PROLIPOSOME BASED TRANSDERMAL DELIVERY OF KETOCONAZOLE . J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-31.

CRIHS-CHEM-001

SYNTHESIS AND IN VIVO BIOLOGICAL EVALUATION OF NOVEL CHALCONES WITH METHYL SULPHONYL END AS POTENT ANTI-INFLAMMATORY AGENTS

Lakshminarayanan B ^{1,2*}, Kannappan N ^{1*}, Subburaju T ²

¹ Department of Pharmacy, Annamalai University, Chidambaram-608002, Tamilnadu, INDIA.

² Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Ahalia School of Pharmacy, Palakkad-678557, Kerala, INDIA.

Email: blnrpharma@gmail.com, lakshmi.narayanan@ahalia.ac.in

ABSTRACT

Eleven new chalcones bearing methyl sulphonyl groups at para position were synthesized from the reaction between 4-methylsulphonylacetophenone and different para substituted aromatic aldehydes by Claisen-Schmidt condensation. The structures of newly synthesized molecules were elucidated by spectroscopic methods such as IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, mass spectra and elemental analysis data. These compounds were screened for their anti-inflammatory activity by carrageenan-induced rat paw edema model in Albino wistar rats. Many of the synthesized compounds behave as inhibitors of leukocyte migration and the formation of pleural exudates when given orally. Thus it can be concluded that all the tested compounds possess significant anti-inflammatory activity in rats. Further studies involving the mechanism of anti-inflammatory action and the effect on gastric irritation may yield a potent anti-inflammatory agent with a low toxicity and better therapeutic index.

KEYWORDS: Chalcones, Methyl sulphonyl group, Anti-inflammatory activity, Leukocyte migration.

How to cite this Abstract:

Lakshminarayanan B, Kannappan N, Subburaju T. SYNTHESIS AND IN VIVO BIOLOGICAL EVALUATION OF NOVEL CHALCONES WITH METHYL SULPHONYL END AS POTENT ANTI-INFLAMMATORY AGENTS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-32.

CRIHS-CHEM-002

ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF THE NOVEL FATTY ACYL CONJUGATES OF ROSUVASTATIN

Arifa Begum SK *, Swathi Goud S *, Shailaja Ch, Sindhu K, Balakrishna, Charan, Ravi Teja and Sree Vasudha K

Avanathi Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Guntapally, Ranga Reddy, Telangana, INDIA.

Email: arifa.medchem@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Fatty acid-conjugating drugs has been developed as a popular strategy to extend the stability of therapeutic agents, improve oral bioavailability, improve targeting to the lymphatic system, to enhance tumor targeting, reduce toxicity and also for a improvement of number of different therapeutic actions, e.g antibacterial activity, anti cancer etc. Rosuvastatin belongs to a stable polar methane-sulphonamide group provides low lipophilicity and enhanced ionic interaction with HMG-CoA reductase enzyme thus improving its binding affinity to this enzyme. Despite its therapeutic potential, the low oral bioavailability of rosuvastatin (20%) suggests that novel approaches are at high requirement in order to improve national heart health. Tagging of the drug to lipophilic carriers improves their efficacy by enhancing their cellular uptake and membrane transport. Falling into the category of chemically-modified drugs, are esters of fatty acids that are lipophilic in nature. Based on the above observations it was planned to design fatty acid conjugates of Rosuvastatin and screen them for the antibacterial activity. The results of antibacterial activity suggest that the Stearic acid conjugated derivative (5), was more active against Gr+ve bacteria with zone of inhibition of 11mm which is almost comparable to Norfloxacin with zone of inhibition of 16mm at 100µM concentrations. The results thereby implicate that the Stearic acid conjugate of rosuvastatin may be a potential antibacterial agent against Gr +ve strains. To gain insights on the molecular interactions the molecular docking studies were also performed. Good correlation was observed between antibacterial activity and in silico studies.

KEYWORDS: Rosuvastatin, Fatty acyl Conjugates, Anti bacterial activity, Molecular Docking.

How to cite this Abstract:

Arifa Begum SK, Swathi Goud S, Shailaja Ch, Sindhu K, Balakrishna, Charan, Ravi Teja and Sree Vasudha K. ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF THE NOVEL FATTY ACYL CONJUGATES OF ROSUVASTATIN. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-33.

CRIHS-CHEM-003

A CHEMOMETRIC ASSISTED RP-HPLC METHOD FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF CHLORDIAZEPOXIDE AND AMITRIPTYLINE HYDROCHLORIDE IN BULK AND PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORMS. Jayaseelan ^{1*}, Dr. N. Kannapan ²^{1*} Research Scholar, Department of Pharmacy, Annamalai University Chidambaram, Tamilnadu, INDIA.² Professor, Department of Pharmacy, Annamalai University Chidambaram, Tamilnadu, INDIA.Email: jayaseelanna@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

A Simple, rapid, precise, and accurate RP-HPLC method was developed and optimized with the help of chemometric tool for the simultaneous estimation of chlordiazepoxide and amitriptyline hydrochloride in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form. Optimization was done by central composite design in response surface methodology. Based on the trial and error, percentage of organic phase in mobile phase, flow rate, and molarity of the buffer were selected as factors. Resolution and retention time were used for the estimation of system response during the optimization procedure. The good separation was achieved on the Kromasil C18 column (150 × 4.6 mm; i.d, 5 μparticle size) using the suitable ratio of the mobile phase containing organic and buffer at a flow rate of 1 mL/min with shorter run time of 5 minutes. The optimized RP-HPLC method was validated as per ICH Q2(R1) guideline. Based on the validation results hence the proposed method was found specific, robust, accurate and sensitive for the determination of chlordiazepoxide and amitriptyline hydrochloride in bulk and tablet dosage form.

KEYWORDS: RP-HPLC, Bulk, Pharmaceutical dosage form, Chlordiazepoxide and Amitriptyline Hydrochloride.**How to cite this Abstract:**

S. Jayaseelan, Dr. N. Kannapan. A CHEMOMETRIC ASSISTED RP-HPLC METHOD FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF CHLORDIAZEPOXIDE AND AMITRIPTYLINE HYDROCHLORIDE IN BULK AND PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-34.

CRIHS-CHEM-004

DISSOLUTION METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF NAPROXEN FROM FIXED DOSE COMBINATION OF NAPROXEN AND ESOMEPRAZOLE MAGNESIUM IN DELAYED RELEASE TABLETS

Devi Thamizhanban *, Kathiresan Krishnaswamy

¹ Department of Pharmacy, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar, Tamil Nadu, INDIA.

Email: devrajmphd@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Dissolution testing method was developed and validated for the evaluation of dissolution behaviour of Naproxen from Naproxen and Esomeprazole magnesium in delayed release tablets 500mg/20mg and 375mg/20mg. Dissolution method was established at acid stage using 0.1N HCl for 2hrs at 75 RPM and at buffer stage using pH 7.4 phosphate buffer for 45 minutes at 100RPM using USP apparatus-2 with Japanese sinker. Chromatography method was carried out using RP-18 HPLC Column, 100 mm x 4.6 mm, Xterra, 5µm particle analytical column with the mobile phase containing mixture of Buffer and Acetonitrile in the ratio 60:40 v/v respectively at a flow rate of 1.0ml/min using UV detector at 305nm. The developed method has been statistically validated according to ICH guidelines and found to be simple and precise with the prescribed values. The linearity was observed in the concentration range of 2.82-83.57µg/ml and 27.86-836.24µg/ml and the mean % recoveries obtained were found to be 99.4-100.0% and 99.92-100.24% respectively for Naproxen in acid stage and buffer stage.

KEYWORDS: Naproxen, Esomeprazole magnesium, RP-HPLC, TRIS buffer, Method validation.

How to cite this Abstract:

Devi Thamizhanban, Kathiresan Krishnaswamy. DISSOLUTION METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF NAPROXEN FROM FIXED DOSE COMBINATION OF NAPROXEN AND ESOMEPRAZOLE MAGNESIUM IN DELAYED RELEASE TABLETS . J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-35.

CRIHS-CHEM-005

METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR THE BIOANALYSIS OF AN ANTIHYPERTENSIVE DRUG USING LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY COUPLED WITH TANDEM MASS SPECTROMETRY

Sanelly Pereira *, Celina Nazareth, Vidhi Bhanushali, Pooja Shelar

PES's Rajaram and Tarabai Bandekar College of Pharmacy, Ponda, Goa-403401, INDIA.

Email: sanelly12@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In this present work, a novel, sensitive and selective method has been developed and validated using liquid chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry for the bioanalysis of irbesartan in human plasma containing an anti-coagulant using its labeled internal standard. Sample pretreatment involved the use of solid phase extraction cartridges followed by chromatographic separation of the analyte on a high resolution column having dimensions of 100x4.6mm and 5 μ particle size. In the developed method the analyte eluted within a runtime of 2.0 minutes using Buffer: Acetonitrile in the ratio of 20:80, v/v as the mobile phase and at a flow rate of 1 mL/min. The relatively shorter period of runtime presents a method for fast and precise quantification of the analyte. The method was validated for the fundamental validation parameters as per the EMEA guidelines for bioanalytical method validation and all parameters were found to be within the acceptable limits. Stability studies were carried out and the results complied with the acceptance criteria.

KEYWORDS: Liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry, Bioanalysis, Solid phase extraction, Human plasma.

How to cite this Abstract:

Sanelly Pereira *, Celina Nazareth, Vidhi Bhanushali, Pooja Shelar. METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR THE BIOANALYSIS OF AN ANTIHYPERTENSIVE DRUG USING LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY COUPLED WITH TANDEM MASS SPECTROMETRY. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-36.

CRIHS-CHEM-006

BIOANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR A DIURETIC DRUG BY LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY TANDEM MASS SPECTROMETRY

Shubham Joshi *, Celina Nazareth, Abhijeet Prabhudessai

PES's Rajaram and Tarabai Bandekar College of Pharmacy, Ponda, Goa-403401, INDIA.

Email: joshi1515@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

A sensitive and rapid liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) method was developed for the determination of hydrochlorothiazide in human plasma using its deuterated internal standard. Sample pre-treatment involved solid phase extraction using cartridges followed by liquid chromatography using a high resolution column having dimension of 100 x 4.6 mm, 5 μ . The analyte was eluted using a combination of acetonitrile: buffer in ratio of 80:20 v/v as the mobile phase. The flow rate of 1 mL/min was employed. The drug was eluted within a run-time of 2.5 minutes. The developed method was validated for bioanalytical studies according to EMA guidelines and the parameters were found to be compliant to the guidelines. Stability studies were conducted on the developed method and results were within acceptable limits. The developed and validated method was found to be faster and economical compared to previous reported methods and can be used for pharmacokinetic studies.

KEYWORDS: LC-MS/MS, Solid phase extraction.

How to cite this Abstract:

Shubham Joshi, Celina Nazareth, Abhijeet Prabhudessai. BIOANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR A DIURETIC DRUG BY LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY TANDEM MASS SPECTROMETRY. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-37.

DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF ANALYTICAL METHODS FOR THE ESTIMATION OF CURCUMIN IN THE HERBAL FORMULATION OF HARIDRA BY UV-VIS SPECTROPHOTOMETRY AND RP-HPLC

Panja Srikanth, Huzaifa Naaz, Manjunath S. Yalgatti, Mithun Rudrapal *

Srikrupa Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Siddipet, Telangana, INDIA.

Email: rsmrp@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Background: Haridra (Turmeric) is an herbal drug official in the Indian Pharmacopoeia 2018. It contains dried rhizomes of *Curcuma longa* Linn. Curcumin is the chief active principle present (not less than 1.5 % w/w) in Haridra. Curcumin and related chemical principles (curcuminoids) are believed to be responsible for the medicinal properties of Haridra. Haridra has been used in Indian systems of medicine (Ayurveda, Unani and Siddha) for the treatment of various human disorders. However, many formulations of Haridra are now available in the market and used extensively as antioxidant and anti-inflammatory medications.

Objectives: Due to lack of standardized protocol (as per WHO guidelines), the analytical methods for the evaluation of herbal formulation of Haridra is not well documented. There are many scientific methods reported so far, but they are not appropriately reliable because of their complexity, non-specificity and other limitations. In our study, we therefore made an attempt to develop simple and specific analytical methods for the evaluation of Haridra formulation in terms of the principle marker component, curcumin by UV-Vis spectrophotometry and RP-HPLC.

Methods: Analytical methods were developed for the estimation of curcumin in the marketed herbal formulation of Haridra by UV Spectrophotometry and RP-HPLC (C18). Methanol was used as solvent (or diluent) for the extraction (ultrasonication) of curcumin from the Haridra formulation. The marketed capsule formulation of Haridra was used for the analysis. The developed UV and RP-HPLC methods were optimized and validated in terms of various analytical parameters as per ICH guidelines. Studies were performed individually for specificity, linearity and range, accuracy, precision, ruggedness, robustness and percentage recovery (assay) in triplicate experiments.

Results and Discussion: The λ_{max} of curcumin in methanol was recorded as 418 nm. In UV method, the linearity was found in the concentration range of 1-5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ with correlation coefficient of 0.999. The precision studies of the method exhibited % RSD values less than 2% indicating that the developed method was precise. The percentage recovery of curcumin in UV method was found to be 97.870 %. The RP-HPLC method showed linearity range between 2-10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ with correlation coefficient of 0.999. In precision studies, the % RSD values were less than 2%. In RP-HPLC, the percentage recovery was found to be 98.516 %.

Conclusion: The developed methods are reported to be simple, valid and specific. These methods can be used for the precise estimation of curcumin in any herbal formulation of Haridra without consuming much time at reasonably simple analytical/ instrumental set up. Our newly developed methods are claimed to be reliable for the routine analytical evaluation of herbal formulation of Haridra in terms of the curcumin marker.

KEYWORDS: Haridra, Herbal formulation, Curcumin, UV-Vis spectrophotometry, RP-HPLC, ICH Guidelines.

How to cite this Abstract:

Panja Srikanth, Huzaifa Naaz, Manjunath S. Yalgatti, Mithun Rudrapal. DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF ANALYTICAL METHODS FOR THE ESTIMATION OF CURCUMIN IN THE HERBAL FORMULATION OF HARIDRA BY UV-VIS SPECTROPHOTOMETRY AND RP-HPLC. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-38.

CRIHS-CHEM-008

REVERSE PHASE HIGH PERFORMANCE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHIC TECHNIQUE FOR THE DETERMINATION OF METFORMIN IN PURE AND ITS DOSAGE FORMS

J. Sushmitha *, B. Vinodh Kumar

Sree College of Pharmacy, Nayakulagudem, Kothagudem, Telangana, INDIA.

ABSTRACT

High Performance Liquid Chromatography is now one of the most powerful tools in analytical chemistry. It has the ability to separate, identify, and quantitative the compounds that are present in any sample that can be dissolved in a liquid. In the present investigation, a simple, sensitive, precise and accurate RP-HPLC method was developed for the quantitative estimation of Metformin in bulk drug and pharmaceutical dosage forms. The selected method was used for method development of the drug molecules Metformin as per ICH guidelines. By taking different mobile phases and by changing columns trials have been done and validation process is done for the optimized method. Metformin was freely soluble in ethanol, methanol and sparingly soluble in water. Methanol: TEA Buffer was chosen as the mobile phase. The solvent system used in this method was economical. The %RSD values were within 2 and the method was found to be precise. The results expressed in Tables for RP-HPLC method was promising. The RP-HPLC method is more sensitive, accurate and precise compared to the Spectrophotometric methods. This method can be used for the routine determination of Metformin in bulk drug and in Pharmaceutical dosage forms.

KEYWORDS: Metformin, RP-HPLC, Method Development.

How to cite this Abstract:

J. Sushmitha, B. Vinodh Kumar. REVERSE PHASE HIGH PERFORMANCE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHIC TECHNIQUE FOR THE DETERMINATION OF METFORMIN IN PURE AND ITS DOSAGE FORMS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-39.

CRIHS-COG-001

PHYTOCHEMISTRY AND PHYTOCONSTITUENTS OF *HYDROCOTYLE JAVANICA* AND *PERISTROPHE BICALYCVLATA*

Karthika. S ^{1*}, Dr. N. Kannappan ²

^{*1} Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Al Shifa college of Pharmacy, Perinthalmanna, Kerala, INDIA.

² Department of Pharmacy, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar, Chidambaram, Tamil Nadu, INDIA.

Email: karthikaselvam1990@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Hydrocotyle javanica and *Peristrophe bicalyculata* belongs to the family Apiaceae and Acanthaceae respectively. It is a medium size herb. It is widely cultivated in north east India and south east Asia. All parts of the plant have medicinal properties so it is a very valuable medicinal plant which is utilized in the traditional system of medicine. The objective of the present research work was to ascertain the presence or absence of the major phytochemical constituents in the selected plants of Apiaceae and Acanthaceae families. The results of the phytochemical analysis of these plants showed the presence of important components which have different medicinally effects. The phytochemical analysis of plants has lot of commercial importance also as these may be further exploited on large scale in manufacturing drugs for the cure of various diseases. *H. javanica* has been reported to possess anti-bacterial, anti-fungal, anti-ulcer, anti-tussive, anti-diabetic, anti-pyretic, antioxidant, wound healing activities and *P.bicalyculata* has been reported be the useful remedy for the treatment of Jaundice, Manorhaegia, T.B, Antiseptic and Anti-venom agent in indigenous system of medicine.

KEYWORDS: *Hydrocotyle javanica*, *Peristrophe bicalyculata*, Apiaceae and Acanthaceae.

How to cite this Abstract:

Karthika. S, Dr. N. Kannappan. PHYTOCHEMISTRY AND PHYTOCONSTITUENTS OF HYDROCOTYLE JAVANICA AND PERISTROPHE BICALYCVLATA. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-40.

CRIHS-COG-002

**PHYTOCHEMICAL, ANTI-OXIDANT AND ANTHELMINTIC ACTIVITIES OF AERIAL PARTS OF
ERANTHEMUM CAPENSE LINN**

Anoopa John L *, Dr. N. Kannappan

*Department of Pharmacy, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar, Chidambaram,
Tamil Nadu, INDIA.*

Email: anoopajohnl@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

*The present study was carried out to investigate the phytochemical constituents, in vitro antioxidant potential and anthelmintic activities of *Eranthemum capense* Linn. The dried powdered leaves of *Eranthemum capense* Linn were extracted using petroleum ether, chloroform, ethyl acetate and methanol using a soxhlet extractor and preliminary phytochemical screening was performed using standard protocols. All the extract was evaluated for their potential antioxidant activities using test such as DPPH, hydroxyl radical and superoxide anion radical scavenging abilities. Anthelmintic activity of extract was screened in adult Indian earthworm model. Preliminary screening revealed the presence of bioactive compounds especially phenolics, tannins and steroids in all extracts. The paralytic (11.22 ± 0.260) and death time (28.10 ± 0.885) of methanolic extract was found to be significant ($P < 0.05$) when compared with paralytic (5.30 ± 0.134) and death time (11.35 ± 0.431) of standard albendazole at 100 mg/ml concentration. The results of the present study indicate that the aerial parts of *Eranthemum capense* Linn exhibited strong anti-oxidant activity and possess significant anthelmintic activity and thus it is a good source of antioxidant and anthelmintic constituents.*

KEYWORDS: *Antioxidant, Anthelmintic, *Eranthemum capense* Linn, Albendazole.*

How to cite this Abstract:

Anoopa John L, Dr. N. Kannappan. PHYTOCHEMICAL, ANTI-OXIDANT AND ANTHELMINTIC ACTIVITIES OF AERIAL PARTS OF *ERANTHEMUM CAPENSE LINN*. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-41.

CRIHS-COG-003

BIO QUALITY BOOSTER EXTRACTION OF BIOWAX FROM PLANTS FOR COMMERCIAL APPLICATION

Bodapati Laxmi Manasa *, K.B.H. Sriram, P. Narender Kumar

Malla Reddy Pharmacy College, Maissamaguda, Dhulapally, Hakimpet, Secunderabad-500100, Telangana, INDIA.

Email: kandurisriram1997@gmail.com, manasalbodapati@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Biowax has always been observed that plants, this is due to the presence of an epicuticle wax layer and the plant leaf microstructures. This study will focus more on the chemical compositions of the wax layer. Waxes generally refer to mixtures of long-chain a polar lipids and long-chain fatty alcohols found on the surfaces of plant leaves and fruits as well as in animals, with wax esters as their main constituent. Some waxes originate from minerals, while others are artificially manufactured. Plant surface wax or epicuticle wax is a mixture of hydroxyl fatty acid polymer (cutin) and suberin. Cutin is the outer covering of plant surface wax; whereas suberin is the Biowax was found on underground parts and healed wound surfaces of plants. The main objective of the project was to isolate the bio wax layer of the leaves using the organic solvent extraction method using chloroform and coat it on to the surface of fruits for storage. The isolated bio-wax was subjected to various tests like anti- microbial test and quantitative analysis to check its viability for industrial uses. The result same will be presented.

KEYWORDS: Bio Quality Booster, Biowax and Plants for Commercial Application.

How to cite this Abstract:

Bodapati Laxmi Manasa, K.B.H. Sriram, P. Narender Kumar. BIO QUALITY BOOSTER EXTRACTION OF BIOWAX FROM PLANTS FOR COMMERCIAL APPLICATION. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-42.

CRIHS-COG-004

IN VITRO AND IN VIVO ANTIHYPERGLYCEMIC EFFECT OF ICHNOCARPUS FRUTESCENCES, COMMERCIALY IMPORTANT MEDICINAL PLANT USED IN INDIAN TRADITIONAL MEDICINE

P. Kavitha Baburao *

Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Avanthi Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Hyderabad, Telegana, India.

Email: kavitha71111@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The present study was aimed to evaluate the antidiabetic activity of Ichnocarpus frutescence (L.) R Br. (Apocynaceae) both in in-vitro and in vivo studies. In in vitro analysis I.frutescens extracts exhibited a dose dependant inhibitory effect on carbohydrate hydrolysing enzymes (alpha-glucosidase). In in vivo studies, hyperglycemia was induced in rats by streptozotocin (stz, 30 mg/kg bw). Stz - diabetic rats were treated with 200 mg (/kg bw) of Hexane, ethyl acetate and methanol extracts for 15 days. Treatment with ethyl acetate active fraction showed significant reduction in fasting blood glucose and serum marker levels ($p < 0.05$). Thus the present investigation supports the traditional use of I.frutescens for the management of diabetes.

KEYWORDS: Ichnocarpus Frutescences, Apocynaceae, Hyperglycemia, Streptozotocin, Hexane, Ethyl acetate, Methanol extract.

How to cite this Abstract:

P. Kavitha Baburao. IN VITRO AND IN VIVO ANTIHYPERGLYCEMIC EFFECT OF ICHNOCARPUS FRUTESCENCES, COMMERCIALY IMPORTANT MEDICINAL PLANT USED IN INDIAN TRADITIONAL MEDICINE. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-43.

CRIHS-COG-005

PHYTOCHEMICAL INVESTIGATION THE ROOTS OF ICHNOCARPUS FRUTESCENS

Gauri Pai Angle *

* Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacognosy, PES's Rajaram and Tarabai Bandekar College of Pharmacy, Ponda, Goa, INDIA.

Email: gauri.angle@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

A large number of medicinal plants are claimed to be of great value in treating diseases in all traditional systems of medicine. *Ichnocarpus frutescens* (Linn) (Family-Apocynaceae) is an evergreen plant and various parts of this plant are used as a cure for fever, dyspepsia, skin troubles and headache. It also has analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties, reduces fever, and lowers fasting glucose and improves glucose tolerance in diabetes. From the literature survey it was revealed that phytochemical groups such as steroids, terpenoids, flavonoids, alkaloids, saponins and tannins were present in different parts of the plant. It was learnt that no substantial work on the roots of *Ichnocarpus frutescens* was carried out. Hence an effort was made to investigate the chemical constituents in ethanolic extract of the roots of *Ichnocarpus frutescens*. Chemical investigation of the roots of *Ichnocarpus frutescens* led to the isolation of five compounds identified as n-nonadecanyl benzoate, benzocosanyl arachidate, β -sitosterol, ursolic acid, quercetin and campesterol from ethanolic extract. None of these compounds has been isolated earlier from roots of the plant.

KEYWORDS: *Ichnocarpus frutescens*, Apocyanaceae, Root.

How to cite this Abstract:

Gauri Pai Angle. PHYTOCHEMICAL INVESTIGATION THE ROOTS OF ICHNOCARPUS FRUTESCENS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-44.

CRIHS-COG-006

EVALUATION OF NIRGUNDI TAILA

Chari A ¹, Tadka H ^{2*}, Yeriswamy H ³, Yernal R ⁴, Krishna MJ ⁵ and Joshi AB ⁶^{1,2} Post Graduate Scholars, Dept. of Pharamcognosy, Goa College of Pharamcy, Panaji, Goa, INDIA.³ Assistant Professor, Dept. of Rasashastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana, GAMRC, Shiroda, Goa, INDIA.⁴ Professor, Dept. of Rasashastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana, GAMRC, Shiroda, Goa, INDIA.⁵ Assisant Professor, Dept. of Pharmacognosy, Goa College of Pharmacy, Panaji. Goa, INDIA.⁶ Professor, Dept. of Pharmacognosy, Goa College of Pharmacy, Panaji, Goa, INDIA.Email: jsnrkmyth@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The branch of Ayurveda which deals with these formulations is known as 'Bhaishajya Kalpana'. One of the important formulations among these is Nirgundi taila. Nirgundi taila is a polyherbal formulation used for treating various ailments since ancient times. It is a combination of leaf powder of Vitex nigundo and Tila taila. It is one of the main remedy in the treatment of pain and abscesses. However, these formulations yet need to be experimented and parameters assessed, to regulate the various limits necessary for the efficient activities, required producing desired therapeutic effect in the patient. The aim of the present study is to evaluate and compare an in-house formulation with those which are already being marketed. Nirgundi taila was prepared using authenticated raw materials. The standard protocol was followed for performing the qualitative evaluation (morphology, microscopy, phytochemical screening, physicochemical investigation, spectroscopical analysis and biological study). The morphological study of colour, odour and taste confirms the identity and authenticity at primary level, while microscopic characters give detail information about the plant materials. The phytochemical and physicochemical investigation showed the presence of various bioactive moieties. And biological test is performed to check the stability of the preparations. Testing on the individual raw materials were carried out to ensure the quality of these before incorporating into the formulation and comparative study between the in-house and the marketed formulations revealed various similarities and dissimilarities in different parameters. This further reiterate the fact that evaluation and development of standard protocols is necessary while dealing with herbal / ayurvedic formulations to meet the international market and improve the national economy.

How to cite this Abstract:

Chari A, Tadka H, Yeriswamy H, Yernal R, Krishna MJ and Joshi AB. EVALUATION OF NIRGUNDI TAILA. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-45.

CRIHS-COG-007

EVALUATION OF TRIPHALA GUGGULU

Pawaskar AN ¹, Naik A ^{2*}, Sudhindra AN ³, Gaurav Desai ³, Krishna MJ ⁵ and Joshi AB ⁶^{1,2} Post Graduate Scholars, Dept. of Pharamcognosy, Goa College of Pharamcy, Panaji, Goa, INDIA.³ Assistant Professor, Dept. of Rasashastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana, GAMRC, Shiroda, Goa, INDIA.⁴ Associate Professor, Dept. of Agadtantra Vyavahar Ayurveda & Vidhi Vaidyaka, GAMRC, Shiroda, Goa, INDIA.⁵ Assisant Professor, Dept. of Pharmacognosy, Goa College of Pharmacy, Panaji. Goa, INDIA.⁶ Professor, Dept. of Pharmacognosy, Goa College of Pharmacy, Panaji, Goa, INDIA.Email: jsnrkmyth@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Ayurveda is a holistic approach which is accepted worldwide because of its wide-ranging intense conceptual basis, profound therapeutic practice and existence of its medicines from ancient periods. Ayurvedic preparations are available as different types of formulations like vatis, churna, bhasma, taila, ghrita, lehya etc. The branch of Ayurveda which deals with these formulations is known as 'Bhaishajya Kalpana'. One of the important formulations among these is Triphala Guggulu. Triphala Guggulu is a polyherbal formulation used for treating various aliment since ancient times. It is a combination of Amalaki, Haritaki, Bibhitaki, Guggulu and Pippali. However, these formulations yet need to be experimented and parameters assessed, to regulate the various limits necessary for the efficient activities, required to produced desired therapeutic effect in the patient. The aim of the present study is to evaluate and compare an inhouse formulation with those which are already being marketed. Triphala guggulu vatis were prepared using authenticated raw materials following ayurvedic procedures. The standard protocol was followed for performing the qualitative evaluation (morphology, microscopy, photochemical screening, physicochemical investigation, spectroscopic analysis and biological study. Testing on the individual raw materials were carried out to ensure the quality of these before incorporating into the formulation and comparative study between the inhouse and two marketed formulations revealed various similarities and dissimilarities in different parameters. This further reiterate the fact that evaluation and development of standard protocols is necessary while dealing with herbal/ayurvedic formulations to meet the international market and improve the national economy.

How to cite this Abstract:

Pawaskar AN, Naik A, Sudhindra AN, Gaurav Desai, Krishna MJ and Joshi AB. EVALUATION OF TRIPHALA GUGGULU. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-46.

CRIHS-COG-008

EVALUATION OF VASA GHRITA

Shet N¹, Desai MS^{2*}, Samant A³, Mohanty D⁴, Krishna MJ⁵ and Joshi AB⁶^{1,2} Post Graduate Scholars, Dept. of Pharamcognosy, Goa College of Pharamcy, Panaji, Goa, INDIA.³ Assistant Professor, Dept. of Rasashastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana, GAMRC, Shiroda, Goa, INDIA.⁴ Associate Professor, Dept. of Agadtantra Vyavahar Ayurveda & Vidhi Vaidyaka, GAMRC, Shiroda, Goa, INDIA.⁵ Assisant Professor, Dept. of Pharmacognosy, Goa College of Pharmacy, Panaji. Goa, INDIA.⁶ Professor, Dept. of Pharmacognosy, Goa College of Pharmacy, Panaji, Goa, INDIA.Email: jsnrkmyth@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Adhatoda vasica is a well-known plant in India which is been constantly used as traditional medicine in household for treatment of cough and cold. Vasa ghrita formulation is prescribed in treatment of bronchial asthama and raktapitta by many ayurvedic practitioners. The main aim was to standardize the Vasa ghrita formulation which is prepared from *Adhatoda vasica* and to establish the standard limits for all the parameters evaluated. In this study Morphological, Microscopical, Phytochemical, Physicochemical and Biological Evaluation was carried out for the crude vasaka and Vasa ghrita formulation which include inhouse vasa ghrita and two marketed formulations brand RVG and brand KKVG. Morphological evaluation was achieved by checking the organoleptic characters. Microscopical study was done by determining the powder microscopy and leaf constants. Phytochemical screening was done to indicate the presence of alkaloids, saponins, carbohydrate, protein, glycosides, tannins, Flavonoids, steroids etc. In physicochemical evaluation many parameters were determined including LOD, Ash values, extractive values, swelling index, foaming index, specific gravity, rancidity, melting point, saponification value, iodine value, acid value, peroxide value, unsaponifiable matter, TLC and HPTLC, FTIR spectroscopy, total phenolic content, total flavonoid content, and DPPH radical scavenging activity. Biological study was done in which microbial load for bacteria and fungi were determined. Parameters evaluated for crude powder and the vasa ghrita formulations were within the standard limits. Study proved that Inhouse vasa ghita was more efficient than Brand RVG and Brand KKVG respectively.

How to cite this Abstract:

Shet N, Desai MS, Samant A, Mohanty D, Krishna MJ and Joshi AB. EVALUATION OF VASA GHRITA. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-47.

CRIHS-COG-009

PHARMACOGNOSTICAL EVALUATION AND QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS OF *BOERHAAVIA DIFFUSA* L. ROOTS

A. Rajesh *

Sree College of Pharmacy, Nayakulagudem, Kothagudem, Telangana, INDIA.

ABSTRACT

Boerhaavia diffusa L. (Family: Nyctaginaceae) is an herbaceous plant, spreading vine widely distributed in the tropical and subtropical regions in the world. The plants are a rich source of vitamins, minerals, protein and carbohydrate. In Punjab region, the drug is useful for the eye disease and in Bombay used for dropsical swellings. The leaves juice is used in jaundice and the root is generally used in infusion in internal inflammation, laxative, and also in urinary disease. The whole plant extract is hepatoprotective in nature. Various parameters like macroscopy, microscopy, fluorescence analysis as well as extractive value and quantitative phytochemical screening of different extractives were studied. The major components of the extractives like total phenolic, total flavonoids were also estimated respectively. The characteristic of microscopy, physicochemical, fluorescence analysis and quantitative chemical screening were performed in root extractives of the plant material as a mean of authentication.

KEYWORDS: *Boerhaavia diffusa*, Phenolic Content, Flavonoid Content, Quantitative Analysis, Hepatoprotective, Urinary Disease.

How to cite this Abstract:

A. Rajesh. PHARMACOGNOSTICAL EVALUATION AND QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS OF *BOERHAAVIA DIFFUSA* L. ROOTS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-48.

CRIHS-COG-010

PRELIMINARY PHYTOCHEMICAL AND IN VITRO ANTIOXIDANT PERSPECTIVES OF THE LEAF EXTRACTS OF AZIMA TETRACANTHA LAM (FAMILY: SALVADORACEAE)

K. Madhu *

Sree College of Pharmacy, Nayakulagudem, Kothagudem, Telangana, INDIA.

ABSTRACT

Antioxidants are widely used as ingredients in dietary supplements such as superoxide dismutase, ferritin, ascorbic acid. Free radicals oxidation has been implicated in artherosclerosis, cancer occurring in lung, breasts, mouth, skin etc, neurodegenerative disease and inflammatory bowel disease. These above facts paved way to discover a new drug from the selected plant with multiple benefits. The present study was to evaluate the preliminary phytochemical screening, invitro and antioxidant activity of leaf extract of *Azima tetraantha* Lam. The plants were collected, authenticated, extracted by hot percolation and various extractive values such as petroleum ether soluble extractives, ethylacetate soluble extractives, methanol soluble extractives were performed. The fluorescence analysis was done by the UV absorption method, phytochemical screening of the plant was done for the estimation of total amount of alkaloid and flavanoids. The antioxidant studies were performed by the thiocyanate method. The free radical scavenging activity of the different fractions of methanol and ethyl acetate extracts of *Azima tetraantha* Lam was measured using DPPH employing the method of Blois. The superoxide anion scavenging activity of the different fractions of methanol and ethyl acetate extracts of *Azima tetraantha* Lam was performed by Chang. The hydroxyl radical scavenging activity was performed by the method of Kunchandy and Rao. It shows that it possess significant scavenging effect on the free radicals and inhibits peroxidation of lipid components and thereby acts as in effective antioxidant principle. Both methanol and ethyl acetate inhibit the LPO, DPPH, superoxide anion, hydroxyl radical. Ethyl acetate extract posses moderate activity when compared with the activity of ascorbic acid, BHT, Quercetin.

KEYWORDS: Antioxidants, *Azima tetraantha* Lam, superoxide anion scavenging activity hydroxyl radical scavenging activity.

How to cite this Abstract:

K. Madhu. PRELIMINARY PHYTOCHEMICAL AND IN VITRO ANTIOXIDANT PERSPECTIVES OF THE LEAF EXTRACTS OF AZIMA TETRACANTHA LAM (FAMILY: SALVADORACEAE). J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-49.

CRIHS-COG-011

PROTECTIVE EFFECTS OF PHYLLANTHUS FRUIT EXTRACT IN ADRIAMYCIN INDUCED GENOTOXICITY IN BONE MARROW CELLS OF MICE

G. Sangeetha *

Sree College of Pharmacy, Nayakulagudem, Kothagudem, Telangana, INDIA.

Email: dara.hari@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

Adriamycin (ADR) is the most commonly used anthracyclin effective in malignant lymphomas and used for various cancers. The aim of the present investigation was to assess the protective effects of curcumin on adriamycin induced genotoxicity on the bone marrow chromosomes of Swiss albino mice. In the present experiment four group of Swiss albino animals were maintained. The experimental group was administered with 4 mg/kg of ADR in a single dose. The subsequent experimental group was administered with Phyllanthus Fruit Extract PFE 340 mg/kg/bw orally for two weeks and on sixteenth day ADR (4 mg/kg/bw) was given intraperitoneally as a single dose. For each experimental group control, animals were maintained. Two days after the administration of the last dose, the animals were sacrificed and air dried metaphase preparations were made and processed for identification of chromosomal aberrations in somatic cells of mice. In animals treated with single dose of ADR, an increase was observed when compared with the values of control group. But when animals primed with PFE + ADR group, there was a decrease in the frequency of chromosomal aberrations. Thus the results clearly indicated the protective role of PFE on adriamycin induced genotoxic damage in somatic cells of mice.

KEYWORDS: Somatic cells, Phyllanthus Fruit Extract, Adriamycin, Chromosomal aberrations.

How to cite this Abstract:

G. Sangeetha. PROTECTIVE EFFECTS OF PHYLLANTHUS FRUIT EXTRACT IN ADRIAMYCIN INDUCED GENOTOXICITY IN BONE MARROW CELLS OF MICE. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-50.

CRIHS-COL-001

INVITRO AND INVIVO ANTI DIABETIC ACTIVITY OF METHANOLIC EXTRACT OF AERIAL PARTS OF ALANGIUM SALVIFOLIUM SUBSPECIE HEXAPETALUM (WANGERIN)

H. Seena *, N. Kannappan, P. Manoj Kumar

Department of Pharmacy, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar, Chidambaram - 608002 Tamil Nadu, INDIA.

Email: seenakannan02@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Alangium salvifolium is a plant which is traditionally used to treat many diseases like laxative, antiepileptic, jaundice, antiulcer agent, pungent, purgative, agent to alleviate spasms, anthelmintic, emetic, antiprotozoal agent, hypoglycemic agent. Its sub specie *Alangium salvifolium* subsp. *hexapetalum* (wangerin) is also known for a variety of traditional use like haemorrhoid, rheumatism and antidote for snake bite. The present work aims for the evaluation of invitro and invivo anti diabetic activity of methanolic extract of aerial parts of *Alangium salvifolium* subsp. *hexapetalum* (wangerin). The invitro antidiabetic activity was evaluated by Starch-Iodine colour assay method. Invivo method was performed by administering orally the methanolic extract of *Alangium salvifolium* subsp. *hexapetalum* in streptozotocin induced male Albino Wistar rats weighing 200g. The study was compared using standard Metformin hydrochloride (10mg/kg) body weight. The invitro method showed a dose dependent anti diabetic activity, that is as the dose increases the percentage inhibition of enzyme activity also increases. Invivo anti diabetic activity was accessed by comparing the body weight and blood glucose level on 0th, 5th, 10th and 15th day using a glucometer. Thus the present study reveals that the methanolic extract of aerial parts of *Alangium salvifolium* subsp. *hexapetalum* (wangerin) were efficient in lowering the blood glucose levels.

KEYWORDS: Antidiabetic, Streptozotocin, Methanolic extract, Metformin hydrochloride, Histopathology.

How to cite this Abstract:

H. Seena, N. Kannappan, P. Manoj Kumar. INVITRO AND INVIVO ANTI DIABETIC ACTIVITY OF METHANOLIC EXTRACT OF AERIAL PARTS OF ALANGIUM SALVIFOLIUM SUBSPECIE HEXAPETALUM (WANGERIN). Title. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-51.

CRIHS-COL-002

ASSESSMENT OF INSULIN RESISTANCE IN DIABETIC FAMILIES

Ch. Madhav Kalyan *, R. Vasudha, D. Uma Bhanu, P. Harika, P. Seetharamiah

Dept. of Pharmacy Practice, Hindu College of Pharmacy, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, INDIA.

Email: maddy.madhav9@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Background Information: Increased prevalence of diabetes in India is due to modern lifestyle changes, unhealthy food habits combined with urbanization. Knowledge about the diabetic diet and the importance of physical exercise in relation to reduce the complications of diabetes is very important and which, in turn, decrease the mortality and morbidity rate.

Objective: The objectives of this study were to assess Insulin resistance and the degree of awareness of diet, physical exercise and lifestyle modifications among family members of patients with Diabetes.

Materials and Methods: 90 patients were included in the study. Those patients who meet the study criteria will be enrolled into the study. This observational study was conducted using Fasting Plasma Insulin, Fasting Plasma Sugar and questionnaire about food habits, physical activity, lifestyle among Type 2 Diabetic family members and HOMA IR value calculated.

Statistical Consideration: All the raw data was collected, entered in SAS 9.4 version. The statistical analysis was done in SAS software by an appropriate statistical procedures like proc means.

Result: The mean age of occurrence of diabetes in study population was found to be 39.5 ± 12.67 years and overall Insulin resistance cases includes 77 severe, 13 moderate, 0 mild. 88 % of the subjects have high insulin resistance and 12% of the subjects have moderate insulin resistance. From our study, it was observed that females were at high risk for development of Diabetes than males and we observed that Diabetes is more prevalent in patients of age group 20 – 30 years.

Conclusion: Despite the clear attitudes of participants towards their dietary pattern and healthy lifestyle modifications, the awareness and the practice were poor among the study group. Effective lifestyle modifications including counselling on weight loss, adoption of a healthy dietary pattern like Mediterranean diet together with physical activity are the corner stone in the prevention of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. Therefore emphasis must be given to promoting a healthier lifestyle and finding solutions in order to increase adherence and compliance to the lifestyle modifications, especially for high-risk individuals.

KEYWORDS: DM, HOMA IR.

How to cite this Abstract:

Ch. Madhav Kalyan, R. Vasudha, D. Uma Bhanu, P. Harika, P. Seetharamiah. ASSESSMENT OF INSULIN RESISTANCE IN DIABETIC FAMILIES. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-52.

CRIHS-COL-003

TEAR METABOLOMICS AN NEW EMERGING TOOL TO DIAGNOSE DRY EYE DISEASE

Tenali Poojitha ^{1*}, Dr. Darabadi Rispa ²

^{1*} Department of Pharmacy Practice, Hindu College of Pharmacy, Amaravati Road, Guntur-522 002. (A.P.), INDIA.

² Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacy Practice, Hindu College of Pharmacy, Amaravati Road, Guntur-522 002. (A.P.), INDIA.

Email: tenalipoojitha2611@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The dry eye disease is a multifactorial syndrome that can be caused by alteration in the quality or quantity of the precorneal tear film. The current methods for diagnostic evaluations and follow up examinations of dry eye disease is a combination of clinical signs and symptoms determined by clinical test respectively. Metabolomics is a new emerging and complementary research discipline to all modern things in the comprehensive analysis of biological system. The identification of specific metabolites and integrated metabolic profiles in patients can potently inform clinicians at an early stage. In ophthalmology metabolomics has gained considerable attention over the past decade but very limited such studies have been replaced on dry eye disease.

KEYWORDS: Metabolomics, Tear metabolomics, Dry eye disease, Precorneal tear film.

How to cite this Abstract:

Tenali Poojitha, Dr. Darabadi Rispa. TEAR METABOLOMICS AN NEW EMERGING TOOL TO DIAGNOSE DRY EYE DISEASE. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-53.

CRIHS-COL-004

A PROSPECTIVE OBSERVATIONAL STUDY ON SAFETY AND EFFECTIVENESS OF ESCITALOPRAM Vs DESVENLAFAXINE IN THE TREATMENT OF ANXIETY DISORDERS

Adapa Prathyusha *, D. Chaitanya, J. Ramya Sri, K. Haritha Chowdary, G. Sadasiva Rao

Department of Pharmacy Practice, Hindu College of Pharmacy, Amaravathi Road, Velangini Nagar, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh-522002, INDIA.

Email: Prathyusha.adapa@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Aim of the study: To study the Safety and effectiveness of SSRI (escitalopram) vs SNRI (desvenlafaxine) antidepressants in the acute treatment of anxiety disorders

Methodology: Patients who are admitted in Manasa Psychiatry Hospital and who meet the study criteria are enrolled into the study. A suitable data collection form was designed for use in the study. Anxiety was assessed by Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale and medication adherence was assessed by Medication Adherence Rating Scale. All the relevant and necessary data for the study was collected from case sheets, interviewing patient & patient's care taker and recorded in data collection forms.

Results: We observed that out of 100 patients, 56(56%) patients were males and 44(44%) patients were females. The people with anxiety mostly belong to the age group of 35-55years. The mean Hamilton anxiety score for desvenlafaxine before treatment was 25.92 and after treatment it was reduced to 16.74. The mean Hamilton anxiety score for escitalopram before treatment was 25.76 and after treatment it was reduced to 22.46. Anxiety symptoms were significantly improved after treatment with SNRI's than SSRI's. High adherence is seen among desvenlafaxine treatment group. Medication Adherence Rating Scale (MARS) of the study concluded that 48% of the patients shown adherence for Desvenlafaxine group and 42% of patients shown adherence for Escitalopram.

Conclusion: We conclude that males are mostly affected with anxiety than females with age group of 35-55years. The present study revealed that desvenlafaxine was associated with significantly greater improvement in anxiety symptoms compared with escitalopram in patients with anxiety.

KEYWORDS: Desvenlafaxine, Escitalopram, Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale, Medication Adherence Rating Scale.

How to cite this Abstract:

Adapa Prathyusha, D. Chaitanya, J. Ramya Sri, K. Haritha Chowdary, G. Sadasiva Rao. A PROSPECTIVE OBSERVATIONAL STUDY ON SAFETY AND EFFECTIVENESS OF ESCITALOPRAM Vs DESVENLAFAXINE IN THE TREATMENT OF ANXIETY DISORDERS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-54.

CRIHS-COL-005

TOPICAL CADEXOMER IODINE VERSUS SALINE DRESSING IN THE MANAGEMENT OF ACUTE AND CHRONIC EXUDING WOUNDS

Sahitya Uppada *, M. Sri Priya, P. Vijaya Sree, K. Sai Tejaswi, Dr. B. Praveena

Department of Pharmacy Practice, Hindu College of Pharmacy, Amaravathi Road, Velangini Nagar, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh-522002, INDIA.

Email: sahityauppada@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Background Information: Due to low base rate of complete healing in the natural history, exuding wounds have a significant impact on the health and quality of life. Cadexomer iodine contains 0.9% iodine within a three-dimensional starch lattice, formed into spherical microbeads. In this study, topical cadexomer iodine ointment was used to determine its effect in the healing process of acute and chronic wounds.

Materials and Methods: It is a prospective observational cohort study which involves 100 patients suffering from various types of exuding wounds and was divided into 2 cohorts (test- topical cadexomer iodine and control- normal saline dressing). Bates-Jensen wound assessment tool was used for the comparison of effect of test and control treatments on wound healing.

Results: After 10 weeks of observation, Topical Cadexomer Iodine demonstrated significant changes in all the parameters involved in wound healing; reduction in pain and odour more efficient than normal saline dressing.

Conclusion: Topical Cadexomer Iodine is more effective than normal saline in the management of various types of exuding wounds; improvement of all parameters involved in wound healing; reduction of pain and odour.

KEYWORDS: Exuding wounds, Cadexomer Iodine, Bates-Jensen Wound Assessment Tool.

How to cite this Abstract:

Sahitya Uppada, M. Sri Priya, P. Vijaya Sree, K. Sai Tejaswi, Dr. B. Praveena. TOPICAL CADEXOMER IODINE VERSUS SALINE DRESSING IN THE MANAGEMENT OF ACUTE AND CHRONIC EXUDING WOUNDS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-55.

CRIHS-COL-006

DRUG UTILISATION EVALUATION & COST ANALYSIS OF ANTI-EMETIC DRUGS PRESCRIBED IN ONCOLOGY WARD IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

Chaitanya. D *, Lavanya. P

Hindu College of Pharmacy, Amaravathi road, Guntur, AP, India-522002.

Email: chaitudakarapu@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

Drug utilization evaluation (DUE) is a system of ongoing, systematic; criteria based evaluation of drug use that will help to ensure that medicines are used appropriately (at the individual patient level). Drug utilization is defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) as the marketing, distribution, prescription, and use of drugs in society, with special emphasis on the resulting medical, social, and economic consequences, Types include, quantitative or qualitative. Quantitative study is done to obtain the variation of drug use and costs of drug therapy, from which medical and social qualitative consequences can be found. It also provide the base from which further qualitative research can be conducted. Our study emphasizes on knowing the drug utilization and cost included for antiemetics in patients undergoing chemotherapy in oncology ward. Total of 141 patients were studied, out of which 77(54.6%) patients were female and 64(45.4%) were male. Majority of the patients in this study belong to the age group of 40-49(29%) and 60 – 69 (20%) years. The comparison with the standard protocol was made according to the use of antiemetics in the patients. Out of which 137(97%) patient profiles were found to be deviating from standard protocol and 4(3%) patient profiles were found following the standard protocol because of including prochlorperazine which is not mentioned in the standard protocol. Deviation of cases without considering prochlorperazine was found to be 74% deviating and 26% not deviating compared to the results where prochlorperazine was included.

KEYWORDS: Drug Utilisation Evaluation, Quantitative, Anti-emetics, Chemotherapy, Prochlorperazine.

How to cite this Abstract:

Chaitanya. D, Lavanya. P. DRUG UTILISATION EVALUATION & COST ANALYSIS OF ANTI-EMETIC DRUGS PRESCRIBED IN ONCOLOGY WARD IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-56.

CRIHS-COL-007

THE IMPACT OF METABOLIC SYNDROME ON RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS: A COHORT STUDY

Ganesh. B*, Sahitya Uppada

Hindu College of Pharmacy, Amaravathi road, Guntur, AP, India-522002.

Email: ganeshboddu1609@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Aim of the Work: To assess the impact of metabolic syndrome on the pattern and clinical presentation of rheumatoid arthritis, and its relation to disease activity and functional status of the patient.

Patients and Methods: Sixty rheumatoid arthritis patients were equally grouped into those with metabolic syndrome (group A) and those without (group B). The disease activity score (DAS-28) and functional status was measured using health assessment questionnaire (HAQ).

Results: The 30 patients with metS had a mean age of 46.3 (27-66 years), disease duration of 5 (3-10) years and the 30 without are of matched age and sex. Joint deformities were detected in 8 patients (26.7%) in group A and in 10 patients (33.3%) in group B. While bone erosions were in 6 (20%) in group A and 7 (23.3%) in group B. As regards the functional capacity, it was found to be more impaired in patients with metS shown by the significantly higher HAQ in Group A than Group B ($p=0.007$). While no significant differences were detected regarding the DAS28 and Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) ($p=0.26$ and 0.13 respectively). In patients with metS (group A), body weight and waist circumference were significantly increased in those with an increased frequency of joint deformities ($p=0.047$ and 0.018 respectively). A significant correlation was found between fasting blood glucose and both joint deformities and erosions ($p=0.016$ and 0.004 respectively).

Conclusion: metS might have a negative impact on RA disease activity and functional status. Regular screening metS in RA patients is recommended.

KEYWORDS: Metabolic Syndrome, Rheumatoid Arthritis, Health Assessment Questionnaire, Visual Analogue Scale.

How to cite this Abstract:

Ganesh. B, Sahitya Uppada. THE IMPACT OF METABOLIC SYNDROME ON RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS: A COHORT STUDY. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-57.

CRIHS-COL-008

EMERGING TRANSDERMAL TREATMENT IN PSYCHIATRY

Beeram Poorna Sivani ^{1*}, Dr. Darabadi Rispa ²

^{1*} Department of Pharmacy Practice, Hindu College of Pharmacy, Amaravati Road, Guntur – 522002, A.P, INDIA.

² Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacy Practice, Hindu College of Pharmacy, Amaravati Road, Guntur – 522002, A.P, INDIA.

Email: sivanireddy2899@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Generally, Transdermal delivery is an alternative therapy for oral routes. With the advent of new transdermal delivery technologies, number of medications is approved in this formulation. Transdermal delivery has more advantages. Here we discuss about the advantages and disadvantages of the Transdermal formulations and use of transdermal treatment in the psychiatry patients. This Transdermal delivery treatment benefits the psychiatry patients, such as effective control of plasma medication concentration, avoidance of first pass hepatic metabolism, less adverse effects, changes in the hepatic abnormalities, improves tolerability. Transdermal delivery treatment can treat many psychiatry conditions and disorders like schizophrenia, Parkinson disease, sleep disturbances and more. In this we discuss mostly about the schizophrenia patients and transdermal delivery treatment fulfils the needs of the patients. This demonstrates about the potential benefits of the treatment and encourages the innovations in the Transdermal delivery treatment in psychiatry patients.

KEYWORDS: Transdermal delivery, Schizophrenia, Psychiatric disorders, Plasma medication concentration, Adverse effects.

How to cite this Abstract:

Beeram Poorna Sivani, Dr. Darabadi Rispa. EMERGING TRANSDERMAL TREATMENT IN PSYCHIATRY. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-58.

CRIHS-COL-009

A STUDY ON INCIDENCE OF PRE-ECLAMPSIA AND ITS NEONATAL OUTCOME

B. Prashanthi ^{1*}, Dr. G. Veeramani ², Dr. A. Madhukar ³

¹ Department of Pharmacy Practice, Assistant Professor, KVK College of Pharmacy, Hyderabad, Telangana, INDIA.

² Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacy Practice, Annamalai University, Chidambaram, INDIA.

³ Associate Professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, MRM College of Pharmacy, Hyderabad, Telangana, INDIA.

Email: prashu13593@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Pre-eclampsia is one of the leading causes of mortality and morbidity to both mother and neonates worldwide. WHO estimates the incidence (or number of new cases) of pre-eclampsia to be seven times higher in developing countries than in developed countries. The exact etiology of is still unknown. This is a Prospective, observational study conducted in SVS Medical College and Hospital, Mahabubnagar. Cases were collected, who were diagnosed with Pre eclampsia from Inpatients of obstetric and gynecology department in duration of six months. A total of 628 cases of pregnant women's were observed among them 52 cases were found with Pre eclamptic patients. The incidence was found to be 8.28%. In age group of < 20yrs it was observed that the incidence is high (63.46%). Most common risk factor associated with Pre eclampsia is Nulliparity, 32 patients (61.53%). In neonatal outcome, the condition at birth- 45 cases (86.53%) were found to be alive and 7 dead cases (13.46%) were seen. The study concluded that the incidence of preeclampsia was high. The most common risk factor associated is Nulliparity, consanguineous marriage and women with high body mass index. Among the neonatal outcome most of them were born with Low birth weight. So there is need for patient education and public health awareness, education of primary health to improve maternal and neonatal prognosis.

KEYWORDS: Pre eclampsia, Incidence, Nulliparity, Neonatal outcome.

How to cite this Abstract:

B. Prashanthi, Dr. G. Veeramani, Dr. A. Madhukar. A STUDY ON INCIDENCE OF PRE-ECLAMPSIA AND ITS NEONATAL OUTCOME. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-59.

CRIHS-COL-010

A STUDY ON MATERNAL AND FETAL OUTCOME ON OLIGOHYDRAMNIOUS PATIENTS

Ch. Shilpa ^{1*}, Dr. V.P. Mahesh Kumar ², Dr. A. Madhukar ³

¹ Department of Pharmacy Practice, Assistant Professor, KVK College of Pharmacy, Hyderabad, Telangana, INDIA.

² Department of Pharmacy Practice, Assistant Professor, Annamalai University, Chidambaram, Tamilnadu, INDIA.

³ Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Associate Professor, MRM College of Pharmacy, Hyderabad, Telangana, INDIA.

Email: shilpasunny44@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Oligohydramnios is one of the common complications diagnosed more frequently these days due to usage of ultrasonography. The aims of the study is to study the maternal and fetal effects of Oligohydramnios, to evaluate the causes Oligohydramnios, to evaluate the perinatal morbidity and mortality. The study is conducted in a rural area after satisfying inclusion and exclusion criteria. Few cases of Oligohydramnios were randomly selected. Borderline Oligohydramnios are monitored by fetal surveillance test on outpatient basis. All cases of severe Oligohydramnios are admitted and evaluated by NST and Doppler study. Maternal and perinatal outcome is assessed. Results were analysed based on percentages and proportions. In our study majority of cases are from rural areas (92%). There is no difference in booked or unbooked status of patients. Common age group is 20 to 25 years. The incidence of Oligohydramnios in our study is 4%. Most common cause of Oligohydramnios is idiopathic. Other common causes are PIH(20%) post dates (12%)and congenital anomalies(2%). 47% of patients had caesarean section. common indication being fetal distress(17%) neonatal admissions were 13% and meconium aspiration syndrome in 6% of babies. Perinatal mortality rate is 6%in our study. Every case of Oligohydramnios needs evaluations of gestational age, cause of Oligohydramnios, monitoring of fetus in the antepartum and intra partum for optimum perinatal outcome.

KEYWORDS: Maternal, Fetal, Oligohydramnios.

How to cite this Abstract:

Ch. Shilpa, Dr. V.P. Mahesh Kumar, Dr. A. Madhukar. A STUDY ON MATERNAL AND FETAL OUTCOME ON OLIGOHYDRAMNIOUS PATIENTS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-60.

CRIHS-COL-011

EVALUATION OF ANTIDEPRESSANT ACTIVITY OF *SPIRULINA PLATENSIS*

Dr. K. Hemamalini *

* Principal, Swami Vivekananda Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Vangapally, Yadagirigutta, Yadadri- Bhongir- 508286, Telangana, INDIA.

Email: rkhemamalini@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Depression is one of the most common psychiatric disorders and according to WHO it is expected to become the second leading cause of disease related to disability by the year 2020. So in search for the novel pharmacotherapy from medicinal plants for psychiatric illness, a trial was made with the plant Spirulina plantensis which is a common plant available in Telangana region. The leaf was chose for the study and extracted with methanol and performed antidepressant activity using forced swimming test (FST) and tail suspension test (TST) using albino mice. Imipramine (10mg/kg) was used as a standard and the dose for the test drug was 200mg/kg. The Spirulina plantens exhibit significant decrease in duration of immobility in FST and TST models which help us to conform the antidepressants activity for the extract when compare to that of the standard. The animal model produced physical stress and lead to depression. The immobility has been expected to reflect to adapt to the stress. Standard drug acts by inhibiting NE reuptake, which increases availability of NE and 5HT at post synaptic site. This is the possible mechanism for the antidepressant activity for the plant extract when compared to that of the standard.

KEYWORDS: Antidepressant activity, Spirulina platensis.

How to cite this Abstract:

Dr. K. Hemamalini. EVALUATION OF ANTIDEPRESSANT ACTIVITY OF SPIRULINA PLATENSIS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-61.

CRIHS-COL-012

EPIDERMODYSPLASIA VERRUCIFORMIS

A. Shwetha

SRR College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Valbhapur, Elkaturthy, Warangal, Telangana, INDIA.

Email: shwethasamuel2@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Is an extremely rare dermal disease informally known as Tree man syndrome. The disease is caused by rare autosomal recessive hereditary genetic disorder located on chromosome 17 which causes mutation on EVER1 and EVER2 genes. An abnormality in MHC class 2 allele DC-DQ has also been documented in patients in America, Europe, Africa continents. These mutations increased vulnerabilities to human papillo virus (HPV) causing uncontrolled growth of scaly macules and papules, prominent in arms, neck and legs. The common initial detection of Epidermoplasia verruciformis is through biopsy on predicted premalignant and malignant skin lesions. Further confirmatory analysis can be performed by in-situ hybridization and polymerase chain reaction. The medical treatment is generally not definitive, typically with topical drugs such as ad imiquimod, 5-flourouracil, vitamin-A derivative 13-Cis retionic acid, interferon alpha or cholecalciferol analogues (vit-D) for severe cases, surgical procedures to remove excessive warts are necessary.

KEYWORDS: Infections, Tree man syndrome, Epidermodysplasia, Scaly macules and papules.

How to cite this Abstract:

A. Shwetha. EPIDERMODYSPLASIA VERRUCIFORMIS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-62.

CRIHS-COL-013

A STUDY OF MEDICATION ERRORS IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

V. Shivani

Malla Reddy Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Hyderabad, Telangana, INDIA.

Email: shivanivaleysa.1997@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Aim: To evaluate the occurrence of medication errors in tertiary care hospitals.

Objectives: A prospective and observational study was conducted in general medicine and orthopaedic ward of Malla Reddy Narayana Hrudayala Hospital, Hyderabad during August -2018 to January-2019. Medication errors were categorized as prescription error, dispensing error, administration error. The case records and treatment charts were reviewed.

Results: A total of 300 patients (150 in general medicine and 150 in orthopaedic ward) were included during the study period. Total number of MEs was 108(36%) of which, 56(38%) were in general medicine and 52(35%) were in orthopaedic wards. The most common MEs was PEs 70(65%) followed by AEs 33(31%).

Conclusion: There is a need to establish ME reporting system to reduce its incidence and improve patient care and safety.

KEYWORDS: Medication Errors, Tertiary Care Hospital.

How to cite this Abstract:

V. Shivani. A STUDY OF MEDICATION ERRORS IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-63.

CRIHS-COL-014

THE CONCEPT OF ALLOSTASIS

D. Gayathri *, Dr. Shyam Sunder

Balaji Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Lakhnepally (V), Narsampet (M), WGL (Dist), Telangana, INDIA.

Email: sonygayathri8@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Allostasis is the process of achieving stability or homeostasis through physiological and behavioral change. It can be carried out by means of alteration in HPA-axis hormones, autonomic nervous system, cytokines or a number of other systems and is generally adaptive in short term the concept of allostasis was proposed by Sterling and Eyer in 1988. By using a balance between energy input and expenditure as the basis for applying concept of allostasis two types of allostatic load have been proposed. Type-1 allostatic load occurs when energy demand exceeds supply resulting in activation of emergency life history stage which directs individual into survival mode. Type-2 allostatic over load begins when there is sufficient or even excess energy consumption accompanied by social conflict and other types of social dysfunction the later is the case in human society and in some situations effecting animals in captivity. Allostasis provides compensation for various problems like heart failure, kidney failure and hepatic failure.

KEYWORDS: Allostasis, Allostatic load, Neuroendocrinology, Energy.

How to cite this Abstract:

D. Gayathri, Dr. Shyam Sunder. THE CONCEPT OF ALLOSTASIS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-64.

CRIHS-COL-015

EVALUATION OF RATIONAL USE OF ANTIBIOTICS FOR SURGICAL PROPHYLAXIS

B. Prashanth Naidu

Malla Reddy Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Hyderabad, Telangana, INDIA.

Email: prashanthroy1997@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Aim: To evaluate the rational use of antibiotics as surgical prophylaxis and assess the patient knowledge regarding the usage of antibiotics.

Methods: This was a prospective, observational study in which a total of 250 in patients subjected for surgical procedures in gynecology and obstetrics, orthopedics and general surgery admitted in Malla reddy Narayana hospital, Hyderabad were included. The study has begun the approval of ethics committee.

Results: We assessed 250 cases of which 75 gynecology and obstetrics surgical cases of which 33.3% & 36% of Pre & Post-operative antibiotics were according to guidelines and 66.6% & 64 % were deviated, Out of 75 orthopedic cases 28 % & 44% of Pre & Post OP are as per guidelines were as 72% & 56 & were not. 100 General surgery cases were assessed & found to be Pre & Post- OP cases 58% & 82% were as per guidelines where as 34% of Pre & 17% of Post OP deviated from guidelines.

Conclusion: The current study revealed that there is inappropriate usage of antibiotics both preoperatively and post operatively. The most common mistake was selection of antibiotic which deviated from guidelines. Patient counseling regarding the antibiotic usage is also important.

KEYWORDS: Prophylaxis, Surgical site infection, rational use, ASHP guidelines.

How to cite this Abstract:

B. Prashanth Naidu. EVALUATION OF RATIONAL USE OF ANTIBIOTICS FOR SURGICAL PROPHYLAXIS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-65.

CRIHS-COL-016

PREVALENCE OF SUB-CLINICAL HYPOTHYROIDISM AMONG DIABETES MELLITUS PATIENTS WITH VASCULAR COMPLICATIONS

Soujanya Srinivas *, Sai Saran Thokada, Harsha Kandregula

Chilkur Balaji College of Pharmacy, Hyderabad, Telangana, INDIA.

Email: soujanyasrinivas7936@gmail.com, tsaisaran11@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Diabetes mellitus and thyroid dysfunction are the two most commonly seen endocrine disorders in outpatient care with reported global prevalence ranging from 2.2 to 17 %. Thyroid dysfunction is a spectrum of disorders of thyroid gland which manifest either as hyper or hypothyroidism. In this case we noticed different circulating levels of TSH. Studies have found that thyroid dysfunction is much, in diabetic population compared to non diabetic population, diabetic and thyroid disorders have been shown to influence each other mutually because of various pathological reasons. The prevalence of hypothyroidism is also influenced by gender, age and other genetic factors. Publications were identified through keyword searches of electronic database and the internet. The databases included are PubMed, Medline, Trip Medical Database, Embase, Cochrane Library and Science Direct. Beta extraction included information about study information, interventions, search strategy, type of review. The extraction was carried out from the studies that were identified for inclusion. Type 2 diabetic patients with subclinical hypothyroidism are associated with an increased risk of nephropathy and cardiovascular events. The clinical importance of the biochemical abnormalities is not clear. Microvascular complications have been most commonly observed.

KEYWORDS: Subclinical Hypothyroidism, Diabetes mellitus, Prevalence, Vascular complications.

How to cite this Abstract:

Soujanya Srinivas, Sai Saran Thokada, Harsha Kandregula. PREVALENCE OF SUB-CLINICAL HYPOTHYROIDISM AMONG DIABETES MELLITUS PATIENTS WITH VASCULAR COMPLICATIONS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-66.

CRIHS-COL-017

MANAGEMENT AND TREATMENT OF CEREBRAL PALSY IN CHILDREN

KL. Keerthana *, Padmakar. S, K. Sujan Kumar

Chilkur Balaji Collge of Pharmacy, Aziz Nagar, Moinabad Road, Hyderabad, Telangana, INDIA.

Email: keerthanakavalipati1998@gmail.com, spadmakar717@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Cerebral refers to brain. Palsy can mean weakness for paralysis or lack of muscle control. Therefore cerebral palsy is a disorder of muscle control which results from some damage to part of the brain. Cerebral palsy is a group of permanent disorders of development of movement and posture, causing activity limitation that are attributed to non-progressive disturbances that occurred in the developing fetal or infant brain. The motor disorders of cerebral palsy are often accompanied by disturbances of sensation, perception, cognition, communication and behavior by epilepsy and by secondary musculoskeletal problems. Approximately 80% to 90% of children with cerebral palsy have spastic cerebral palsy. The diagnosis of the spasticity in the children with the cerebral palsy requires a complete physical examination with ancillary testing as needed. The aim of treatment is to encourage the child to learn to be independent as possible. Some children who have mild cerebral palsy will not have any problems in achieving independence. For others it will be a slow process. In some with severe difficulties, considerable assistance from others will always be needed. Specific treatment varies by individual and changes as needed if new issues develop. In general, treatment focuses on ways to maintain or improve a person's quality of life overall health.

KEYWORDS: Cerebral Palsy, Management, Treatment, Children.

How to cite this Abstract:

KL. Keerthana, Padmakar. S, K. Sujan Kumar. MANAGEMENT AND TREATMENT OF CEREBRAL PALSY IN CHILDREN. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-67.

CRIHS-COL-018

EFFECTS OF BLOOD GLUCOSE LEVELS WERE STUDIED BY USING CANDESARTAN CILEXETIL AND GLIMIPIRIDE IN NORMAL AND DIABETIC ALBINO MALE RATS

V. Manisha *, P. Srinivasulu

Chilkur Balaji Collge of Pharmacy, Aziz Nagar, Moinabad Road, Hyderabad, Telangana, INDIA.

Email: manishavemula1998@gmail.com, vasusri38cology@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Effects of blood glucose levels was studied by using candesartan cilexetil and Glimepiride in normal and diabetic albino male rats at a dose of 1.44 MG per KG and 0.09 MG per KG respectively. The blood samples were subjected to estimation of blood glucose levels using glucometer. Glimepiride showed hypoglycemic effect at 4th hour, whereas Candesartan cilexetil doesn't show any changes in blood glucose level in both normal and diabetic right. In normal rats Candesartan clixetil doesn't effect on the blood glucose levels of Glimipiride in single and multiple doses. In diabetic rats Candesartan clixetil show significant action on blood glucose levels of Glimepiride in my tupelo interaction steady but insignificant effect of Candesartan clixetil in single dose interaction on Glimipiride. Hence the interaction with carefully monitored in time to diabetics mellitus patient.

KEYWORDS: Diabetes, Glucose Levels, Candesartan Cliental, Glimepiride, Albino rats.

How to cite this Abstract:

V. Manisha, P. Srinivasulu. EFFECTS OF BLOOD GLUCOSE LEVELS WERE STUDIED BY USING CANDESARTAN CILEXETIL AND GLIMIPIRIDE IN NORMAL AND DIABETIC ALBINO MALE RATS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-68.

CRIHS-COL-019

A STUDY OF FRESH FRUIT JUICE OF (HYBRID PERCENTAGE)-MALUS DOMESTICA X M.SYLVESTRIS AGAINST EXPERIMENTALLY INDUCED ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE IN MICE

Aniruddha Banerjee *, Vineetha M, Karunakar Hegde

Department of Pharmacology, Srinivas College of Pharmacy, Mangalore- 574 143, Karnataka, INDIA.

Email: aniruddhab0197@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

This study was designed to evaluate fresh fruit juice of (HYBRID PERCENTAGE)-malus domestica x m.sylvestris for Alzheimer's disease in mice. The cognitive enhancing activity of fruit juice on scopolamine induced memory impairment in mice was investigated by using behavioural parameter viz, Morris water maze (MWM), Passive shock avoidance paradigm (PSAP) and estimation of biochemical parameter in terms of AchE activity. Two doses (1ml/kg) and (1.5ml/kg, b.w, p.o) of juice were subjected for the study against experimentally induced Alzheimer's disease in mice using scopolamine (0.4mg/kg, i.p). Piracetam (400mg/kg, i.p) was served as standard in both the models. The long term administration of both the low (1ml/kg) and high dose (1.5ml/kg) of juice produced significant reduction of transfer latency (TL) and escape latency time (ELT) ($P < 0.01$) and ($P < 0.05$) in PSAP and MWM respectively. An increase of time spent in target quadrant (TSTQ) value in MWM model on both 19th and 27th day when compared to control and induced groups was observed. The fruit juice at higher dose significantly ($p < 0.01$) reduced the activity of AchE in the brain indicates the improvement in learning and retention of memory in young mice. From the above data it is concluded that fresh fruit juice of (HYBRID PERCENTAGE)-malus domestica x m.sylvestris was found to be effective against amnesia induced by scopolamine in experimentally in Alzheimer's mice.

KEYWORDS: Morris water maze, Nootropic, Passive shock avoidance paradigm, Scopolamine.

How to cite this Abstract:

Aniruddha Banerjee, Vineetha M, Karunakar Hegde. A STUDY OF FRESH FRUIT JUICE OF (HYBRID PERCENTAGE)-MALUS DOMESTICA X M.SYLVESTRIS AGAINST EXPERIMENTALLY INDUCED ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE IN MICE. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-69.

CRIHS-COL-020

EVALUATION OF ANTI-ANXIETY ACTIVITY OF AQUEOUS EXTRACT OF PUMPKIN (*CUCURBITA MAXIMA*) SEEDS IN MICE

Grinton Veigas *, Saisree PM, Karunakar Hegde

Department of Pharmacology, Srinivas College of Pharmacy, Mangalore- 574 143, Karnataka, INDIA.

Email: grin2veigas@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

*This study was performed to investigate the anxiolytic effects of aqueous extract of pumpkin (*Cucurbita maxima*) seeds in mice using the elevated plus-maze model (EPM) and light dark model. The extract administered orally in two different doses of 100mg/kg and 200mg/kg and evaluated for the number of entries and time spent in both open and closed arm of EPM model and light dark model. This effect was comparable to that of Diazepam (1.0mg/kg, i.p). These results indicate that extract is an effective anxiolytic agent. The animals treated with extract (100mg/kg and 200mg/kg) increased the time spent and the number of arm entries in the open arms of the elevated plus-maze, also increased the time spent by mice in the illuminated side of the light-dark test, in comparison with control animals. The above data revealed that *Cucurbita maxima* seeds were found to be helpful in treating anxiety in both the models. In our study, initially it was clear that *Cucurbita maxima* seeds contained tryptophan and it helps to reduce anxiety. In conclusion the present data indicate that the administration of *Cucurbita maxima* seed extract to mice showed significant anxiolytic activity.*

KEYWORDS: Anxiety, *Cucurbita maxima*, Elevated plus maze.

How to cite this Abstract:

Grinton Veigas, Saisree PM, Karunakar Hegde. EVALUATION OF ANTI-ANXIETY ACTIVITY OF AQUEOUS EXTRACT OF PUMPKIN (*CUCURBITA MAXIMA*) SEEDS IN MICE. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-70.

CRIHS-COL-022

PHARMACOLOGICAL SCREENING AND PHYTOCHEMICAL EVALUATION OF ANTI-DIABETIC ACTIVITY OF ASPARAGASUS RACEMOSUS LEAVES IN NORMAL AND ALLOXAN INDUCED DIABETIC RATS

T. Somasekhar *

Sree College of Pharmacy, Nayakulagudem, Kothagudem, Telangana, INDIA.

ABSTRACT

Diabetes mellitus is a most common endocrine disorder, affecting more than 300 million people worldwide, we studied the anti-diabetic potential of leaves of A.Racemosus. The acute oral toxicity studies of the extracts revealed no toxic effects up to the levels of 2000mg/kg b.wt. The aqueous and alcoholic extracts of 20 and 30mg/kg body weight of A.Racemosus was screened for the presence of hypoglycemic and antidiabetic activity. In this study diabetes was induced by a single IP dose Alloxan monohydrate in 72hrs fasted rats. The FBGL was carried on 7th, 14th and 21st day and OGTT was measured on 8th, 15th and 22nd day. Glibenclamide was taken as the standard and the results are quite comparable with it. The studies were indicated that the leaves of A.Racemosus are effective in regeneration of insulin secreting β -cells and thus possess antidiabetic activity. The aqueous and alcoholic extracts showed significant effect in decreasing the Fasting blood Glucose level and oral glucose tolerance test of rats and it's also showed good hypoglycemic activity in normal glycemic rats. The preliminary phytochemical analysis of the extracts of A.Racemosus revealed the presence of alkaloids, tannins, saponins, terpenoids, flavonoids, phenolics and glycoside as the possible biologically active principles.

KEYWORDS: *A. Racemosus, Alloxan monohydrate, Glibenclamide, FBGL and OGTT.*

How to cite this Abstract:

T. Somasekhar. PHARMACOLOGICAL SCREENING AND PHYTOCHEMICAL EVALUATION OF ANTI-DIABETIC ACTIVITY OF ASPARAGASUS RACEMOSUS LEAVES IN NORMAL AND ALLOXAN INDUCED DIABETIC RATS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-71.

CRIHS-COL-023

A RETROSPECTIVE OBSERVATIONAL STUDY ON THE ASSESSMENT AND TREATMENT PATTERN OF DIFFERENT TYPES OF EPILEPTIC SEIZURES IN PEDIATRICS

Rajesh Oruganti *, Rajkumar Venishetty

Chaitanya College of Pharmacy Education & Research, Hanamkonda, T.S, INDIA.

ABSTRACT

Background: An epileptic seizure is a period of symptoms due to abnormally excessive or synchronous neuronal activity in the brain. Outward effects vary from uncontrolled shaking movements involving much of the body with loss of consciousness (tonic-clonic seizure), to shaking movements involving only part of the body with variable levels of consciousness (focal seizure), to a subtle momentary loss of awareness (absence seizure). A seizure that lasts for more than a brief period of time is a medical emergency. In this study, we aimed to assess the different types of seizures with respect to their manifestation and treatment.

Methods: The present study was conducted in the department of paediatrics at Amrutha Hospital, Hanamkonda, between January 2019 and June 2019. It is a prospective study in which children of age New born to 12 years with a clinical diagnosis of epileptic seizures were included.

Results: From the total admissions of the PICU, the frequency of the children who are affected by the Seizures was found to be 68% for the males and 31.3% for the females which are in the present study. The percentage for males in the types of seizures observed in the study which includes Afebrile, Febrile, GTCS and Focal were (10%, 28.6%, 14.7%, 15.3%) respectively and the corresponding values for the females were (5.3%, 14.7%, 6%, 5.3%). It is observed therefore that the occurrence of Febrile seizures account for the major presence of epileptic seizures in paediatrics followed by Focal, GTCS and Afebrile seizures (in males), Febrile seizures, GTCS, Focal and Afebrile seizures respectively (in females).

Conclusion: In the present study, among all types of seizures the prevalence and incidence rate was found to be more with Febrile seizures. As seizures possess a relatively varied mortality rate in children the early recognition and patient education is required.

How to cite this Abstract:

Rajesh Oruganti, Rajkumar Venishetty. A RETROSPECTIVE OBSERVATIONAL STUDY ON THE ASSESSMENT AND TREATMENT PATTERN OF DIFFERENT TYPES OF EPILEPTIC SEIZURES IN PEDIATRICS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-72.

CRIHS-GEN-001

SOFT SKILLS - A MOMENTOUS FOR PHARMACY STUDENTS

K. Sreevasudha * and SK. Arifa Begum

Avanathi Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Guntapally, Ranga Reddy, Telangana, INDIA.

Email: sreevasudha7@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Pharmacy the healthcare profession ensures to provide the proper medication and proper counseling to the patients and requires the people skills or social skills or core skills or employability skills merely soft skills. Mastering these soft skills makes professional life prosperous. With the changing inclination and malleable educational courses, the competition for job accretion is becoming more resilient. The top 7 propensities like Communication Skills, Team-work, Adaptability, Problem Solving, Critical Observation, Leadership Skills and Conflict Resolution are more strenuous to teach because of its prevail aspects.

Communication Skills: Both verbal and non-verbal along with written communication skills for building healthy relationships with everyone and also to boost one's performance.

Team work: Hirelings can synthesize their diverse talents and everyone wins.

Adaptability: Teaches how to adapt various shifts and the environment.

Problem Solving: helps how to steer unexpected challenges.

Critical Observation: Being a critical observer can help you in molding yourself a better person all around.

Conflict Resolution: It helps to foster a blooming and communal environment everywhere.

Leadership Skills: Leadership means inspiring and helping others to reach their full prospect. Remember soft skills aren't optional because job success depends only on soft skills. So, students regard soft skills as an important part of their skills set and their ability to practice the profession.

The globe needs smart Pharmacists those can communicate effectively, work as a team to provide the best.

KEYWORDS: Communication skills, Adaptability, Soft skills, Conflict resolution.

How to cite this Abstract:

K. Sreevasudha and SK. Arifa Begum. SOFT SKILLS - A MOMENTOUS FOR PHARMACY STUDENTS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-73.

CRIHS-GEN-002

3D-BIOPRINTING - REVOLUTIONARY TECHNOLOGY: A BRIEF FOCUS

G. Sravani *, S. Swetha *, R. Sai Kiran, Rafqua Zeb and SK. Arifa Begum

Avanthi Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Gunthapally, Rangareddy, Telangana, INDIA.

Email: arifa.medchem@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Drug development costs necessitate the continuous research for economical means without compromising the results. Three dimensional (3D) bioprinting is currently emerging as revolutionary technology enabling clinical treatments using a patient's own cells which can reduce the chance of rejection and also eliminate the need for organ donors. It focuses on vast applications, in areas viz., manufacturing, medicine, architecture, custom art and design by use of 3D printing-like techniques to combine cells, growth factors, and biomaterials for fabricating biomedical parts that imitate natural tissue characteristics. 3D bioprinting provides personalized medication based on the genetic profile and health condition of the patient. Recently, the technology has even made advancements in the production of cartilage tissue for use in reconstruction and regeneration, for reduction of organ trafficking etc. Tissue models developed using this technique can decrease the preclinical trial costs by eliminating the need for animal models in drug discovery and cosmetic testing. Currently, bioprinting can be used to print tissues and organs to help research and also in printing of scaffolds which can be used to regenerate joints and ligaments. In the future, bioprinted tumour models created using a patient's own cancerous cells could revolutionize the cancer therapy.

KEYWORDS: 3D bioprinting, Tissue models, Revolutionary technology and Anticancer.

How to cite this Abstract:

G. Sravani, S. Swetha, R. Sai Kiran, Rafqua Zeb and SK. Arifa Begum. 3D-BIOPRINTING - REVOLUTIONARY TECHNOLOGY: A BRIEF FOCUS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-74.

CRIHS-GEN-003

WHAT DO YOU THINK WILL HAPPEN TO “CANCER” IN COMING “10 YEARS”? - THE UPCOMING INNOVATION: CANCER CELL TO FAT CELL

Sumaiyya Mehreen *, Arifa Begum SK

Avanathi Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Guntapally, Ranga Reddy, Telangana, INDIA.

Email: arifa.medchem@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Cancer being the most affected disease almost all over the world the statistics are very well known among 1 in 2 people are affected with the cancer and the female being more prone to it. Where in women the most common type of cancer is “BREAST CANCER.” In spite of the chemo therapy, immunotherapy or the surgical treatments there is a continuous demand for the new innovations. Is there any other treatment other than surgery or therapy? Can it not be cured without all that? Partially or completely? So, in a recent research it was found out that the cancerous cells present in the breast when introduced into the female mice, and treated with cocktail of 2 FDA approved drugs (Rosiglitazone; an anti-diabetic drug & Trametinib; a drug used for the treatment of cancer) converted to harmless fat cells and stopped the metastasis. As every research has its pros and cons the cons here were that not all the cancerous cell got converted to harmless fat cells but the cells which got converted remained in the same state. This result showed the positive era for new lines of treatment. Still this hasn't been tested on human volunteers but sooner or later after all the satisfactory results in the coming time researchers would be successfully doing it, as this include an optimistic side just because the cocktail of drugs which they used are already approved by FDA for human use. Let's hope that the conversion of cancer cells to fat cells would be a breakthrough in cancer therapy.

KEYWORDS: Cancer therapy, Cancer cells to Fat cells, Innovations.

How to cite this Abstract:

Sumaiyya Mehreen, Arifa Begum SK. WHAT DO YOU THINK WILL HAPPEN TO “CANCER” IN COMING “10 YEARS”? - THE UPCOMING INNOVATION: CANCER CELL TO FAT CELL. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-75.

CRIHS-GEN-004

POSTPARTUM DEPRESSION - A REVIEW

Dr. A. Rajani

Associate Professor, MNR College of Pharmacy, Hyderabad, Telangana, INDIA.

ABSTRACT

Postpartum Depression is a type of depression that women are affected after giving birth to an infant. The condition develops within 4-6 weeks after giving birth, but it can sometimes take several months to appear. Depression is usually caused by emotional, stressful events, a biological change triggering an imbalance of brain chemicals. The factors that lead to PPD are physical changes of pregnancy, excessive worry about the child and responsibilities of being a parent, lack of family support, loneliness, and history of mental health, financial crisis and many others. Symptoms include low mood lasting for more than a week, crying a lot, feeling of guilt, lack of appetite, headaches, panic attacks, and disturbed sleep patterns. PPD is diagnosed by asking the patient to complete a depression screening questionnaire. The most important step to treat PPD is to acknowledge the problem. Family, partners and friends support have a major impact on faster recovery. Self help groups are beneficial. Medications like anti depressants are prescribed to balance the chemicals in the brain that effect mood changes. Tricyclic antidepressants like imipramine and nortriptyline are usually prescribed.

KEYWORDS: Postpartum, panic attacks, self help groups, Tricyclic depression.

How to cite this Abstract:

Dr. A. Rajani. POSTPARTUM DEPRESSION - A REVIEW. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-76.

CRIHS-GEN-005

AMYGDALIN (VITAMIN B₁₇) - A REVIEW ON ANTICANCER PROPERTY

Kokonda Soundarya ¹, Shailaja Ande ²

¹ Vision college of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research, Hyderabad, Telangana, INDIA.

² Avanthi Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Hyderabad, Telangana, INDIA.

Email: genuine.shaila@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Amygdalin is a cyanogenic glycoside, obtained from the pebbles of rosaceous fruits, like apricots, almonds, cherries, peaches and plums, with is traditionally used as antitumor drug. Amygdalin induces apoptosis in cancer cells .It is composed of two molecules of glucose, one of benzaldehyde, which induces an analgesic action, and one hydrocyanic acid , which is antineoplastic compound. Cancer is the result of metabolic disorder caused by a vitamin deficiency.it states further that laetrile or amygdalin/vitamin B 17,is the missing vitamin needed by the body to restore health. Rhodanese enzyme plays a major role.

KEYWORDS: Amygdalin, Rhodanese, Cyanogenic glycoside.

How to cite this Abstract:

Kokonda Soundarya, Shailaja Ande. AMYGDALIN (VITAMIN B₁₇) - A REVIEW ON ANTICANCER PROPERTY. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-77.

CRIHS-GEN-006

CRIPSR-THE NEW TOOL IN THE GENE EDITING TO PREVENT CANCER

Komal Yadav, N. Neeraja, Shailaja Ande *

Department of Pharmacology, Avanthi Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Hyderabad, Telangana, INDIA.

Email: genuine.shaila@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The purpose of the present study was to block the cancer mutations and to slow down the growth of cancer cells. It can be done by using a new gene-editing tool called CRIPSR abbreviated as (clustered regularly interspaced short palindrome repeats), which was first discovered in 1987 in *Escherichia coli* and later been used in humans. It is a powerful gene-editing tool, that allows genome editing at specifically targeted location. This therapy involves removal of immune cells from cancer patients. These immune cells are then modified with the gene editing tool i.e., (CAS9). CRIPSR turned off a gene that shows down the immune response in cancer patients. Generally the CRIPSR includes two molecules,

- ❖ DNA cutting enzyme called as CAS9
- ❖ A piece of RNA molecule that acts as a guide for the enzyme.

The CAS9 enzyme follows the guide RNA in the same location. Once it reaches its destination, CAS9 enzyme cuts the target DNA at specific point. Not only that scientists are hoping to start phase-1 clinical trials, to treat patients with genetic disorder called BETA-THALASSEMIA.

Conclusion: In this way the scientist can replace a defective gene with a healthy one.

KEYWORDS: Mutation, palindrome, CAS9/CRIPSR, Virally driven cancers.

How to cite this Abstract:

Komal Yadav, N. Neeraja, Shailaja Ande. CRIPSR-THE NEW TOOL IN THE GENE EDITING TO PREVENT CANCER. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-78.

CRIHS-GEN-007

GREEN BLOOD

Maddela Srikanth, Shailaja Ande *

Department of pharmacology, Avanthi Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Hyderabad, Telangana, INDIA.

Email: genuine.shaila@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Green blood is extracted from wheat grass, which consists of carbohydrates, proteins and all essential mineral and vitamins. Wheat grass juice bears a closer resemblance to the haemoglobin in our blood the juice is often called as GREEN BLOOD and the therapy is called as Green blood therapy. Wheat grass juice consists of over hundred elements, they have been isolated by scientists and concluded that it is a complete food, only 140 g of fresh wheat grass is the nutritional equivalent of 3 kg of the choicest vegetables, has been scientifically proved that molecule of human blood haemoglobin and chlorophyll of wheat grass are exactly same and the pH of haemoglobin and wheat grass is 7.4. Wheat grass is green because of chlorophyll unlike human blood which is red.

KEYWORDS: Wheat grass, Haemoglobin, Chlorophyll.

How to cite this Abstract:

Maddela Srikanth, Shailaja Ande. GREEN BLOOD. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-79.

CRIHS-GEN-008

INJECTABLE BONE CEMENT

B. Bharath Kumar, Shailaja Ande *

Department of pharmacology, Avanthi Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Hyderabad, Telangana, INDIA.

Email: genuine.shaila@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

A toothpaste like substance that may get rid of painful bone grafts. The bone substitute material can be injected minimally invasively into a bone defect with a suitable injection apparatus. IBC is a class of materials that are initially in either liquid or paste form which can be either be injected through a channel or molded into shape. After certain period of time the IBC solidifies in order to make the shape of the site of implantation and aids the regeneration of new bone tissue.

- A) In good healthy bone stock the fixation of a fracture is maintained with metallic screws.
- B) In osteoporotic bone, there is a risk of implant loosening and displacement of the fracture.
- C) The surrounding osteoporotic bone is strengthened using injectable bone cement (Green)

Clinically used recent IBC materials are polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA), Calcium phosphate bone cement (CPC) calcium sulfate based bone cement (CSC)

Composition: Tricalcium phosphate anhydrous dicalcium phosphate and mono calcium phosphate monohydrate.

Conclusion: There are three main reasons that support the use of nonmaterial's in order to improve IBC over micron scale materials the presence of microparticlas can act as larger stress cone points and crack initiation sites the roughness and nanoscale surface features generated by nanoparticles are favorable for protein adsorption and osteoblast activity.

KEYWORDS: Injectable bone cement, Polymethylmethacrylate, Ossification.

How to cite this Abstract:

B. Bharath Kumar, Shailaja Ande. INJECTABLE BONE CEMENT. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-80.

CRIHS-GEN-009

SKIN GLUE

M. Sangamithra, Shailaja Ande *

Department of Pharmacology, Avanthi Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Hyderabad, Telangana, INDIA.

Email: genuine.shaila@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Skin glue replaces stiches in modern trade through the ages, a wide range of materials have been used to close deep cuts and other wounds including cobwebs, in modern medicine, stiches and staples. But now, another material is glue. Rather than put patients through the long painful or deal of removing the stiches as a week. Doctors are finding that they can simple the edges together and send their patient home. Strong adhesive substance especially a hard protein chiefly gelatinous substance that absorbs water to form a viscous solution with strong adhesive property. The glue is applied as a liquid or paste to the edges of the wound. The glue is used for close wounds is commonly known as "Super gluecyanocrylaye or Liquid Stripes" Modern trade skin glue: Dermabond, Epiglu, Periacryl

Conclusion: *It's a modern measure that requires no anaesthesia , less skill and mainly painless. It needs no stiches.*

KEYWORDS: *Glue, liquid stripes.*

How to cite this Abstract:

M. Sangamithra, Shailaja Ande. SKIN GLUE. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-81.

CRIHS-GEN-010

METAGENESIS TO ADIPOGENESIS

D. Sri Shruti ¹, P. Kavitha Baburao ^{2*}

¹ Vision College of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research, Hyderabad, Telangana, INDIA.

^{2*} Avanthi Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Hyderabad, Telangana, INDIA.

Email: kavitha71111@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Harmful cancer cells turned to harmless fat cells. The breast cancer which is a complicated cancer, probably most risky cancer in women is no more dangerous now. Research studies have now brought out a new way of converting cancer cells to fat cells because fat cells are incapable of dividing themselves. Experimentation on mice with the help of combination of Rosiglitazone and Trametinib have paved way to cancer cell invasion, dissemination and metagenesis that lead to the formation of harmless fat cells. Researchers are looking forward to experiment this in human beings.

KEYWORDS: Metagenesis, Adipogenesis, Rosiglitazone, Trametinib, Cell invasion, Dissemination.

How to cite this Abstract:

D. Sri Shruti, P. Kavitha Baburao. METAGENESIS TO ADIPOGENESIS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-82.

CRIHS-GEN-011

INNOVATION IN MOBILE HEALTH CARE TECHNOLOGY

G. Charitha *, SK. Ayesha

SIMS College of Pharmacy, Mangaldas Nagar, Guntur – 522001, A.P, INDIA.

Email: amanicharitha1998@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Pharma research institutes are taking the advantage of mobile health technology to conduct Clinical research. Smartphones with powerful processors and advanced sensors track the movement, take measurements and record information. This is useful in post market studies and allow people to participate in studies more easily. Mobile health app has the potential to engage number of individuals and large geographical areas, Currently apple smartphone has several mhealth including apps targeting parkinsons disease, diabetes, cardiovascular disease, asthma, breast cancer that has been developed by research institutes. Mobile health sensors are not confined to smartphones wearable devices such as smart watches and fitness bands which contains accelerometers and GPS sensors that are capable to take biometric readings now a days these sensors became more innovative, advanced and accurate. Mobile and wearable devices that are able to track heart rate, Body temperature, blood glucose level, blood oxygen level and various measurements that are used in clinical trials. Internet connectivity enables the information they collect to be synced or immediately shared with doctors and researchers. This reduce the need for patients to make visit to a research center or a hospital and participating in any clinical trials.

KEYWORDS: Mobile Health Care, Clinical Research.

How to cite this Abstract:

G. Charitha, SK. Ayesha. INNOVATION IN MOBILE HEALTH CARE TECHNOLOGY. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-83.

CRIHS-GEN-012

BASICS ASPECTS OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS

V. Veeramanikandan *, K. Kathiresan

Department of Pharmacy, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar, Chidambaram, Tamilnadu, INDIA.

Email: dr.kathiresan123@rediffmail.com

ABSTRACT

Intellectual property rights (IPR) have been defined as ideas, inventions, and creative expressions based on which there is a public willingness to bestow the status of property. IPR gives exclusive rights to the inventors or creators of the property, in order to enable them to reap commercial benefits from their trademark, etc. patent is an exclusive monopoly grant by the Government of an inventor over his invention for limited period of time. The present review elaborates all aspects of Intellectual property right in detail along with its protection criteria.

KEYWORDS: Intellectual property, Patent, License, Copyright, Trade mark.

How to cite this Abstract:

V. Veeramanikandan, K. Kathiresan. BASICS ASPECTS OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-84.

CRIHS-GEN-013

LEADS AND DANGERS OF BIOSIMILARS

R. Murali Krishnan *, K. Kathiresan

Department of Pharmacy, Annamalai University, Annamalai Nagar, Chidambaram, Tamilnadu, INDIA.

Email: dr.kathiresan123@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

A biosimilar that has been approved by a regulatory authority in a highly regulated area is like another batch of its reference product but produced by a different manufacturer. A patient should derive the same therapeutic benefit from a biosimilar as from its reference product. A patient treated with a reference product can change to its approved biosimilar without loss of efficacy or an increase in safety risk. A biosimilar should cost significantly less than its reference product and at least a portion of the cost savings realized from using a biosimilar should be passed on to the patient.

KEYWORDS: Regulatory authority, Biosimilar, Efficacy, Therapeutic benefit.

How to cite this Abstract:

R. Murali Krishnan, K. Kathiresan. LEADS AND DANGERS OF BIOSIMILARS. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-85.

CRIHS-GEN-014

A STUDY ON REGISTRATION OF GENERIC DRUGS AND REGULATORY REQUIREMENTS FOR MIDDLE EAST COUNTRIES

V. Mallikarjun

Chaitanya College of Pharmacy Education & Research, Hanamkonda, T.S, INDIA.

ABSTRACT

The main principle according to the GCC Regulation is implementing the registration of all medicines with the Ministry of Health (MOH) in order to be legally circulated in the GCC market. Pharmaceutical product registration is a demanding task in regulated, semi regulated and rest of world countries. Although the requirements are harmonized in regulated countries by CTD (Common technical document) filing, yet others have enormous diversity in requirements. ICH (International conference on Harmonization of Technical Requirements for Registration of Pharmaceuticals for Human Use) brought regulatory authorities and pharmaceutical industries of Europe, Japan and US together for various aspects of drug registration. Similarly, countries from Asia pacific and gulf are in process of harmonization with mutual concern as The Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) and Gulf Co-operation Council (GCC). The quality, safety and efficacy data has its own importance in the registration dossier. The commercial significance of markets is increasing globally. It is vital for pharmaceutical industry to cope with the regulatory requirements for betterment of public and to ensure their place in the market. This paper approaches the registration requirements in the form a dossier for market authorization. It also has drawn a comparative statement on various approaches for harmonization of registration requirement for pharmaceuticals. The Ministry of Health GCC-DR are the main authorities. Despite the government's efforts at modernizing the healthcare system by creating new authorities and issuing new regulations in the last decade, the division of powers and authorities among the various regulatory entities (between the Federal and Emirates levels and between different entities at each level). Any medical company which plans the marketing of its production in the country should be registered in the Ministry.

KEYWORDS: Generics, Regulated, GCC.

How to cite this Abstract:

V. Mallikarjun. A STUDY ON REGISTRATION OF GENERIC DRUGS AND REGULATORY REQUIREMENTS FOR MIDDLE EAST COUNTRIES. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-86.

CRIHS-GEN-015

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE-THE BEGINNING OF A NEW ERA IN PHARMACY PROFESSION

D. Shravya, Taruni, J. Manashwini, R. Vidya, Dr. K. Naresh

Malla Reddy Pharmacy College, Maisammaguda, Dhulapally, Secunderabad-500 014

Email: manashwinigoudjageer@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a branch of computer science that deals with the problem-solving by the aid of symbolic programming. It has greatly evolved into a science of problem-solving with huge applications in business, health care, and engineering. One of the pivotal applications of AI is the development of the expert system. With the advent of big data and AI, robots are now becoming more trustworthy for doctors, and a large number of institutions are now employing robots along with human supervision to carry out activities that were previously done by humans. The major advantage of AI is that it reduces the time that is needed for drug development and, in turn, it reduces the costs that are associated with drug development, enhances the returns on investment and may even cause a decrease in cost for the end user. A large number of researches are being carried out to improve the current available AI technology to make the pharmacy profession more efficient. The present article briefly describes the importance of AI in the process of drug development and then looks at the various AI tools that are available at the disposal of a modern-day pharmacist to aid in a more efficient functioning.

How to cite this Abstract:

D. Shravya, Taruni, J. Manashwini, R. Vidya, Dr. K. Naresh. ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE-THE BEGINNING OF A NEW ERA IN PHARMACY PROFESSION. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-87.

CRIHS-NUR-001

EFFECT OF NESTING AND SWADDLING ON SLEEP DURATION OF PRETERM NEONATE

N. Pahadi, R. Chaudhary *, B. Karn, U. Yadav

Department of Child Health Nursing, College of Nursing, B.P. Koirala Institute of Health Sciences, Dharan, NEPAL.

Email: ramanandc2016@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Introduction: All preterm neonate sleep is disturbed in hospitalization period due to various stressful environmental factors and human error and without focusing in individual developmental care; that impact on neonate neurological development as well as normal growth which caused lifelong disabilities. Nurses play a vital role for preventions of neurological disabilities and normal growth.

Objective: The objective of the study was to assess the effect of Nesting and Swaddling on sleep duration of preterm neonates.

Materials and Methods: True experimental (post-test control design) study conducted among 36 preterm neonates, who were admitted in Nursery and Neonatal Unit of BPKIHS. Consecutive sampling technique was used. Preterm neonates were randomly allocated into two groups to form experimental and control. Proforma was used to collect socio-demographic characteristic and sleep duration was recorded in self-administer observation sheet base on the observational behavior characteristics scoring of neonatal sleep by AASM (American Academy of sleep Medicine). Nesting and Swaddling were done in experimental group then after neonate sleep time was recorded in video; finally analyzed in minute.

Results: There were 23 male (63.9%) and 13 female (36.1%) preterm were enrolled. There were significant different in sleep duration between experimental and control group where the mean sleep duration was 59.22 ± 22.613 in experimental group and 39.50 ± 8.066 in control with p-value 0.001. The mean difference in sleep duration was 19.95 minute in experimental groups and control group.

Conclusion: Nesting and Swaddling can be used as convenient and effective method to increased neonates sleep duration or rest period.

KEYWORDS: Nesting, Swaddling, Effect, Sleep duration, Preterm.

How to cite this Abstract:

N. Pahadi, R. Chaudhary, B. Karn, U. Yadav. EFFECT OF NESTING AND SWADDLING ON SLEEP DURATION OF PRETERM NEONATE. J Sci Res Pharm 2019;8(Suppl 1):S-88.